

New trends in line balancing and model sequencing in assembly, disassembly and machining environments

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Abstract: The Assembly Line Balancing Problem (ALBP), first formally introduced by Salveson in 1955, has long been a foundational topic in operations research and production management. Over the past seven decades, ALBP has evolved significantly—from a straightforward task-to-station assignment problem to a complex, multi-objective optimization challenge that reflects the intricacies of contemporary manufacturing systems. This transformation has been especially pronounced in the last two decades, driven by the integration of Industry 4.0 technologies, increasing emphasis on sustainability, and the emerging human-centered paradigms associated with Industry 5.0. In this article, we review recent advancements and integrate contributions selected for this Special Issue, which builds on papers presented at the IFIP APMS 2021 and IFAC MIM 2022 conferences. With 37 papers selected from over 90 submissions, this Special Issue represents the first dedicated collection on ALBP since the 2006 special issue in the *European Journal of Operational Research* (EJOR), and it reflects the field's remarkable progression during a period of profound transformation in manufacturing.

Keywords: Industry 4.0, Assembly line balancing, Transfer line balancing, Human robot collaboration, Model sequencing, Planning and scheduling, Optimization, Applications of Artificial Intelligence

1 Introduction

The assembly line balancing problem (ALBP) has been a cornerstone of operations research and production management since its formal mathematical introduction by Salveson in 1955. Over seven decades, it has evolved from a simple task-station assignment problem into a complex multi-objective optimization challenge addressing diverse aspects of modern manufacturing systems. This evolution has been particularly remarkable over the past two

decades, as manufacturing has been transformed by Industry 4.0 technologies, sustainability imperatives, and the emerging human-centric focus of Industry 5.0. Originally developed for the automotive industry (Dolgui, 2006, El Ahmadi and El Abbadi, 2022; El Houd et al., 2024; Sordan et al. 2022), line balancing methodologies have more recently been extended to other sectors, including housebuilding (Grenzfurtner et al., 2024), railway freight (Zhang et al. 2023) and the aircraft industry (Bao et al., 2023; Borreguero Sanchidrián et al., 2024; Borsato Pinhão et al., 2022; Lovato et al., 2024).

The first formulations for simple assembly line balancing problem (SALBP) have initially focused on optimizing efficiency by assigning indivisible tasks to sequential workstations while adhering to precedence constraints. The primary objectives have typically been to minimize the number of workstations for a given cycle time (SALBP-1) or to minimize the cycle time for a fixed number of workstations (SALBP-2). However, the increasing complexity of modern manufacturing environments has significantly broadened the framework for line balancing problems for assembly, disassembly and machining production systems (Battaia and Dolgui, 2013). In recent years, several key developments have emerged that have fundamentally reshaped the field (Boysen et al., 2021).

A recent review by Battaia and Dolgui (2022) analyzed the 300 contributions published between 2012 and 2022 and presented 7 main trends in the literature. To assess whether these topics remain prominent in recent literature or if new trends have emerged, we conducted a comprehensive search using the EBSCO database with the keywords “line balancing” OR “model sequencing.” The search was restricted to peer-reviewed journal articles written in English and published between June 2022 and April 2025. This query yielded a total of 467 articles. We excluded 11 articles that had already been analysed in the review by Battaia and Dolgui (2022), leaving 456 articles for further screening. After analysing the abstracts, a final selection of 153 articles was retained based on their relevance to the scope of this study. The subsequent sections first explore the evolution of key research trends in the recent literature, followed by an integration of the articles selected for this Special Issue. The presentation is organized into several thematic sections.

2 Fundamental ALBP Models and Core Contributions to the Field

The digitalization of production systems has greatly expanded access to real-time production data, offering significant opportunities to enhance optimization models. This advancement paves the way for innovative modeling techniques, the introduction of new constraints, and the development of novel mathematical formulations to represent these constraints. However, certain expert-driven data, such as precedence constraints, can be challenging to extract from manufacturing data, as actual production plans are often overconstrained. As a result, the quality of precedence data can undermine the effectiveness of optimization models, leading to issues that require more refined approaches to improve their accuracy and relevance.

In this context, Finnah et al. (2025) addressed the persistent issue of inaccurate precedence data by formulating the Data Validation Problem as a dynamic optimization task. Their approach optimizes the allocation of expert time to validate or correct potentially erroneous precedence constraints, ensuring that the most critical inaccuracies are addressed first. By prioritizing expert validation efforts, their method maximizes the removal of erroneous constraints, thereby improving the feasibility and performance of decision support systems. The authors proposed both optimal and heuristic querying strategies to selectively improve data quality while minimizing validation effort. They show that even limited expert intervention can lead to substantial performance improvements, highlighting the importance of integrating expert-driven validation in real-world optimization efforts.

Further, Fink et al. (2025) argue that despite significant progress that has been made in developing automatic solvers for ALBP over the past several decades, the widespread adoption of such tools in industry has been limited, resulting in a persistent gap between theoretical models and practical applications. Traditional automation approaches assume that all constraints and objectives can be clearly defined and fixed in advance, allowing solvers to generate optimal or near-optimal solutions. However, this assumption does not always hold in practice, where the industrial complexities of production, resources and large task graphs make it challenging to model the problem with sufficient accuracy.

In light of these challenges, Fink et al. (2025) believe that complete automation of ALBP is likely infeasible in practice. According to the authors, the difficulties associated with accurate problem modeling, data collection, and dynamic objective function specification make fully automated solutions impractical for many industrial applications. As a result, human intervention remains essential in the decision-making process. To bridge the gap between theory and practice, the authors propose a decision support system (DSS) that fosters an interactive, iterative workflow to assist engineers in the planning process. Rather than focusing solely on standalone solvers, which treat integration with DSS as a secondary concern, the authors advocate for solvers that are inherently designed to be compatible with decision support workflows. They highlight the critical solver features necessary for effective DSS integration and emphasize the central role of such systems in advancing practical automation for assembly line balancing. This approach attempts to align real-world requirements with research literature and enhances the practical feasibility of optimization efforts in complex industrial environments.

In the context of solving SALBP-1 and SALBP-2, the branch, bound, and remember (BBR) algorithm introduced by Sewell and Jacobson (2012) for SALBP-1, as well as by Li et al. (2021) for SALBP-2, remain among the most efficient exact methods to date. Schulze et al. (2024) adapted the BBR approach to address a variation of the SALBP focused on maximizing workload smoothness. Specifically, they introduced R-SALSA, an advanced version of the SALSA algorithm that targets the SALBP-SX, where the objective is to minimize workload imbalances across stations using a quadratic smoothness index. R-SALSA incorporates a bidirectional branch, bound, and remember strategy combined with dynamic

programming to pre-determine feasible station workloads and generate a construction plan for possible station loads. The algorithm is enhanced through the novel introduction of supporters and preventers to improve branching and bounding efficiency, as well as a tailored heuristic for generating high-quality initial solutions and refined dominance rules. Extensive computational experiments on benchmark datasets demonstrate that R-SALSA significantly outperforms all previous exact methods, solving instances with up to 1,000 tasks.

Despite the strong performance of BBR-based exact methods, Assembly Line Balancing (ALB) problems are inherently NP-hard, making the solution of large-scale instances computationally intensive. In such cases, approximate methods can provide high-quality solutions within more practical time frames. Addressing this need, Álvarez-Miranda et al. (2023) proposed a variable-depth local search algorithm for the SALBP. This approach employs variable-length sequences to navigate the solution space efficiently, improving the best-known solutions for several benchmark instances. The authors also analyze the structural characteristics of problem instances where their algorithm demonstrates superior performance, offering valuable insights into the method's robustness and areas of applicability.

An analysis of recent literature reveals a clear shift from simplified formulations of line balancing problems toward more sophisticated models that integrate multiple optimization components. This emerging trend is examined in detail in the following section.

3 Hybridization with other optimization problems: towards a complexification of formulations

The first direction of increasing complexity involves the transition from single-product assembly lines to mixed- and multi-product line configurations

3.1. Mixed-model lines and model sequencing

Driven by product customization and rapid market shifts, manufacturing companies are increasingly adopting mixed-model assembly lines over traditional single-model lines. To effectively align production capacity with demand variability, one of the major challenges is to determine the optimal sequence of models on assembly lines. While model sequencing and assembly line balancing were traditionally addressed as separate optimization problems, a growing body of research has focused on their integration within a unified framework to better capture their interdependencies and improve overall system performance.

Louis et al. (2023) compare the Mixed-Model Sequencing (MMS) which explicitly incorporates assembly line balancing with Car Sequencing (CS) which relies on sequencing rules to meet plant-specific requirements, such as minimizing work overload for assembly workers. Two exact methods based on Dynamic Programming are developed to evaluate the solution space gap between the models. Numerical experiments, based on real-world manufacturing data from a Renault Group assembly plant, reveal that MMS consistently generates a higher number of feasible sequences compared to CS, regardless of the method used to compute

sequencing rules. Interestingly, only the sequencing rules currently applied by plant schedulers lead to a larger number of distinct feasible sequences under the CS model—yet often at the expense of increased work overload.

Sikora (2024) studies a mixed-model assembly line that incorporates random production sequences. The study optimizes both task assignments and station lengths using a Branch-and-Bound algorithm integrated with Markov chain-based cost evaluations. The method accounts for product variant probabilities—either independent or correlated—and can be refined through sequencing optimization once the production orders are known. Results emphasize that optimizing station lengths significantly reduces total costs, often surpassing the impact of improved task assignments.

Sikora and Tiacci (2025) address the integration of car sequencing rule selection with assembly line balancing for large-scale production systems under uncertain product sequences. By incorporating car sequencing rules, the study reduces the variability in simulated production sequences used to assess the effectiveness of line balancing solutions, without the computational complexity associated with solving a full optimization problem.

Hashemi-Petroodi et al. (2022) explore mixed-model assembly lines with model-dependent task assignments, workforce reconfiguration, and equipment duplication. A MILP formulation is presented to minimize labor and equipment costs. Dualization and heuristic methods are introduced to handle large-scale instances.

Alhomaiddi and Askin (2024) investigate parallel mixed-model assembly lines involving task-dependent tools. Their study considers a simultaneously assignment of tasks to workstations, models to lines, and tools to specific workstations. A mathematical model and a heuristic solution approach are proposed and validated using benchmark datasets.

Peng et al. (2023) tackle balancing and sequencing in flexible MMALs using AND/OR graphs and if-then logic rules to model alternative precedence constraints. The study compares mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) and constraint programming (CP) formulations, supplemented with an iterative decomposition method for scalability. Results indicate that CP outperforms MILP, particularly in instances with a high density of OR relations.

Sawik (2024) develops a novel mixed-integer programming (MIP) model for balancing and scheduling MMALs with disjunctive (AND/OR) precedence constraints. Unlike prior models that require pre-enumeration of all alternative assembly subgraphs, the proposed approach introduces new variables and constraints to implicitly select optimal precedence subgraphs during the solution process.

Mönch et al. (2022) address the concept of Variable Takt Time Groups (VTGs) as a strategic lever for balancing workloads and minimizing operator inefficiencies. The study introduces the concept of workload equilibrium and proposes a heuristic VTG Algorithm to minimize either the number of VTGs or the maximum operator drift per unit. Empirical validation using

data from Fendt and Rolls-Royce Power Systems shows that VTGs outperform fixed takt strategies in labor efficiency.

Huchzermeier and Mönch (2023) study a variable rate launching (VRL) strategy to enhance production flexibility and eliminate utility work and idle time. A mixed-integer model evaluates VRL against fixed rate launching under both open and closed workstation configurations. The study finds that VRL strategies significantly reduce labor costs and total line length, offering compelling advantages in throughput and cost efficiency, especially when task times and station lengths are heterogeneous.

Contribution of the Special Issue:

Zeng et al. (2023) study a mixed hybrid disassembly line—incorporating both non-destructive and destructive disassembly. They propose a MIP model and an improved discrete flower pollination algorithm to optimize the disassembly line with aims to minimize the number of workstations, improve the smoothness index, reduce energy consumption, and maximize disassembly profit.

Liu et al. (2024) propose an evaluation method for estimating remanufacturing assembly time and develops a multi-objective mathematical model for balancing remanufacturing mixed-model assembly lines. The proposed evaluation approach employs the Fuzzy Graphical Evaluation and Review Technique network to predict the expected assembly time for each operation. The multi-objective model aims to simultaneously optimize remanufacturing takt time and the comprehensive balance rate. An Adaptive Double-Layer Genetic Algorithm (ADGA) is designed: the first layer focuses on enhancing production efficiency, while the second layer improves assembly line balancing. The proposed methodology is validated through a case study involving the assembly of high-pressure common rail fuel pumps.

Tiacci (2024b) proposes an integrated approach to simultaneously address Mixed-Model ALBP, buffer allocation between stations, and optimization of the model sequencing for asynchronous lines. A Genetic Algorithm (GA) is combined with discrete event simulation to evaluate individual fitness. Experimental results on a set of benchmark instances quantify the individual and combined effects of sequencing and buffer allocation on line efficiency.

Schibelbain et al. (2024) study the optimization of mixed-model robotic assembly lines. The authors propose a hybrid approach that incorporates a MIP model and performance evaluation conducted through simulations and linear relaxation techniques to estimate the solution quality.

Shang et al. (2024) develop a MILP scheduling model for mixed-model flexible flow lines. A five-level scheduling strategy is proposed, prioritizing on-time and in-full delivery, followed by early production, delayed delivery, reliance on safety stock, and, as a last resort, demand cutting.

Elyasi et al. (2024) consider the context of washing machine production at Vestel Electronics who utilizes 20 assembly lines to produce approximately 200 different washing machine

models. Scheduling decisions must account for several critical constraints, including job-to-assembly line compatibility, release times, due dates, and workload balancing across lines. The primary objective is to minimize the total earliness and tardiness, considering sequence- and machine-dependent setup times, unequal job release times, and job-machine compatibility restrictions. To solve this complex problem, the authors propose a novel metaheuristic algorithm based on the Imperialist Competitive Algorithm.

A second avenue for increasing complexity involves the incorporation of heterogeneous resources into the model.

3.2. Line balancing and heterogenic worker/robot assignment

Several studies focused on the integration of worker/robot heterogeneity and/or skill constraints in ALBPs, recognizing the heterogeneity of operational resources in modern production systems. Pereira and Ritt (2022, 2023) explore a specialized variant known as the Workload Allocation Problem (WAP), originally introduced by Battarra et al. (2020). In this formulation, tasks follow a linear precedence chain, and their execution times vary depending on the assigned worker, reflecting individual productivity differences. WAP represents a constrained case of the broader Assembly Line Worker Assignment and Balancing Problem, where general precedence structures apply. Pereira and Ritt establish the NP-hardness of WAP and propose several lower bounds alongside both exact and heuristic solution methods. Their experimental results demonstrate that the proposed approaches can optimally solve instances with up to 4,000 tasks and 29 workers—approximately twice the size of previously solvable cases—thereby significantly advancing the computational tractability of this problem class.

Pitakaso et al. (2023) address the ALBP type-2 with multi-skilled workers, where the goal is to minimize the cycle time under the constraint of limited machine types per workstation. They use the Variable Neighbourhood Strategy Adaptive Search to solve the problem.

Işık and Yildiz (2024) extend the ALBP with Hierarchical Worker Assignment Problem (ALBHWP) to U-shaped line configurations. In ALBHWP, tasks require different qualification levels, and worker substitution follows a hierarchical cost structure—higher-qualified workers can perform lower-skill tasks at increased cost, but not vice versa. The authors formulate both MILP and CP models to solve this problem. Results indicate that CP models not only outperform IP models in solution quality and computation time but also surpass existing metaheuristic approaches for straight-line configurations.

Lahrichi et al. (2023) address the Robotic ALBP-2 variant, which aims to minimize the cycle time. They consider sequence-dependent setup times, which require determining the order of tasks within each workstation and robot-dependent task and setup times. Two problem variants are explored: one allowing robot types to be assigned to multiple workstations, and another restricting each robot to a single workstation. For the special case where a global sequence of tasks is predefined, a polynomial-time optimal algorithm, termed the "split"

algorithm, is developed. This algorithm is embedded within a metaheuristic framework that explores the space of global task sequences.

A further direction for increasing model complexity involves incorporating multiple workers operating concurrently at the same workstation.

3.3. Line balancing and worker assignment in multi-manned lines

This type of problem typically arises in environments involving multi-manned or multi-robot systems, where workers may either be assigned to fixed workstations or remain flexible, moving among stations as needed. Two-sided assembly lines (TAL) represent a specific case of multi-manned lines, in which the number of resources per station is inherently limited to two—one on each side of the line.

Wei et al. (2023) tackle the Two-sided ALBP-1 using a novel combination of Colored Petri Nets (CPN) and Minimum Spanning Tree algorithms. The authors propose a three-step method: first, a reachability tree chart is built to show potential tasks order assignment, second, the colour firing mechanism is used to evaluate the satisfaction of colored rules; and finally, employing MST logic with a least-time prioritization strategy to allocate tasks effectively.

Kang and Lee (2023) explore a fuzzy multi-objective LP with weights model for TALBP that simultaneously addresses such objectives as minimizing the number of workstations and cycle time, maximizing line efficiency, and minimizing idle time and smoothness index. To manage large-scale and computationally intensive instances, a GA is developed.

All other studies discussed here address two-sided DLBP.

Degirmencioglu Demiralay and Kara (2024) propose a novel MILP to maximize the total net recovery profit. Results showed that implementing two-sided disassembly lines provides 29.18% increment in total net recovery profit compared to the straight line. Furthermore, the effects of different parameter levels on the net recovery profit are analysed using two-way analysis of variance.

Zhang et al. (2022) also develop a MILP model but for four optimisation objectives: the number of mated stations, idle index, demand index, and hazard index. The study redefines the hazard and demand indices and introduces new time constraints specific to mated stations. A multi-objective whale optimisation algorithm is used to solve the problem.

Liang et al. (2022) introduce a probability-based task-destructive disassembly model. The model captures the negative impacts of destructive disassembly tasks on total disassembly cost, workload smoothness, and adjacent but unconnected tasks. A (MIP) formulation is developed to jointly minimize total disassembly cost, workload smoothness index, and the disruptive effect of destructive tasks on neighbouring operations. To solve the problem, a novel multi-objective Restart Genetic Flatworm Algorithm is proposed. The case studies for the disassembly of mobile phones, laptops, printers, and engines are considered.

Multi-manned lines.

Liu et al. (2022) extend the Assembly Line Worker Assignment and Balancing Problem to a risk-averse context involving disabled and temporary workers with uncertain availability. A two-stage stochastic programming model is proposed, where fixed tasks are pre-assigned, and flexible tasks and workers are allocated in the second stage. A hybrid GA incorporating K-means clustering and variable neighborhood search outperforms sample average approximation in both quality and efficiency.

Michels and Costa (2022) address the resource-constrained ALBP type-2 aiming to minimize cycle time under fixed station and resource constraints. Michels and Costa (2024) develop a MILP model and hierarchical heuristics for multi-manned stations with heterogeneous workforce assignment.

Andreu-Casas et al. (2022) analyze the Multi-Manned ALBP incorporating stochastic task durations due to inter-worker interference. Several solution strategies are tested, including a mathematical model and heuristic approaches based on constrained partitioning.

Melega et al. (2024) formulate mathematical models that co-determine the number of parallel workers for each workstation and cycle time, and propose a specialized network flow model for serial task structures.

Kose et al. (2023) examine disassembly lines with multi-manned, heterogeneous workers, emphasizing worker satisfaction alongside classical performance metrics. They introduce a multi-objective MILP model that integrates worker preferences and game-theoretic heuristics.

Güner et al. (2024) propose two optimization methods—MILP and CP—to minimize the number of workers needed in multi-manned assembly lines when sequence-dependent setup times are considered. Computational experiments show that the CP approach outperforms MILP on modified benchmark instances and leads to tangible productivity improvements in real-world scenarios.

Huang and Zhou (2024) study a multi-manned DLBP with worker heterogeneity and collaboration. Their approach accounts for collaborative tasks, skill-based heterogeneity, and safety constraints. A bi-objective MILP model is optimized via a multi-mechanism-enhanced bi-objective African vultures optimization algorithm which incorporates hybrid encoding, advanced decoding, and adaptive neighborhood search.

Şahin and Kellegöz (2023) address multi-manned ALBP involving walking workers, aiming to simultaneously minimize the number of workers and workstations. Several exact solution approaches based on Benders' decomposition are developed to solve the problem to optimality.

Calzavara et al. (2025) investigate the impact of assembly and station time variability on the performance of Walking Worker (WW) systems, in comparison to Fixed Worker (FW) systems, using a simulation-based approach. The influence of the number of workers and workstations, as well as travel time, is analysed. Based on the simulation data and considering target

throughput alongside task time variability, a decision tree and selection procedure are developed to guide the choice between FW and WW configurations.

Yeni et al. (2024) present an integrated approach that combines multi-product, multi-period, and multi-manned disassembly line concepts. A generic optimization model is first formulated and GA-based solution methods are developed. The study explores three tactical-level lot sizing policies—economic disassembly quantity (EDQ), just-in-time (JIT), and random (R). The results emphasize the effectiveness of JIT-based lot sizing, especially as the number of periods increases.

Li and Zhou (2025) address disassembly line balancing by introducing a novel multi-cycle work-sharing strategy that enables task reassignment across sub-cycles to improve workload balance and reduce cycle time. While this strategy significantly enhances disassembly efficiency, it also increases total resource consumption due to the varying resource requirements of different tasks. To tackle this trade-off, the authors propose a bi-objective integer linear programming model that aims to simultaneously minimise cycle time and total resource usage. The ϵ -constraint method is applied to solve small-scale instances, while for larger problems, a Double Deep Q-Network-based Hyper-Heuristic (DDQN-HH) algorithm is developed. This algorithm features custom encoding and decoding schemes, two state functions, and eight heuristic action rules to guide the search process.

Didden et al. (2023) address an ALBP based on a real-world case at VDL Nedcar, incorporating key practical factors such as mixed-model production, sequence-dependent setup times, variable workstations with multiple operators, and multiple assignment constraints. A GA is developed to solve the problem and to serve as a decision support tool. The algorithm is evaluated on newly proposed benchmark instances, revealing that the quality of the solution is influenced by the relationship between takt time, job processing times, and setup times. Furthermore, results from the real-life case study demonstrate that the proposed GA effectively balances the assembly line, leading to improved line efficiency and reduced variance in operation times across different product models compared to current industrial practices.

Schäfer et al. (2025) investigate a new version of ALBP characterized by complex constraints, including the selection of station-specific equipment, the deployment of multiple robots per workstation, and the *non-discrete assignment of tasks*. The proposed approach is applied to a real-world case study from a Tier 1 automotive supplier. A multi-criteria optimization framework is used to evaluate the planning outcomes, which are compared to manual expert planning.

Contribution of the Special Issue:

Şahin and Kellegöz (2024) introduce two novel mathematical modelling approaches, along with a lower bound estimation method, for balancing multi-manned assembly lines involving walking workers. Although the new formulations introduce additional variables, they require

fewer constraints compared to the existing models, resulting in improved computational efficiency.

Gartner et al. (2024) study a wall element prefabrication plant comprising three distinct production lines. Three operational scenarios were defined and analysed to explore job and product rotation strategies aimed at enhancing flexibility and mitigating bottlenecks. In the first scenario, the formation of floater groups was introduced to optimize worker scheduling. The second scenario focused on implementing product rotation to bypass line-specific bottlenecks. The third scenario combined both strategies. The linear optimization model demonstrated improved production planning capabilities across all scenarios.

Yılmaz et al. (2023) investigated the integrated lot streaming and workforce scheduling problem within the context of a seru production system.

Another direction of increasing complexity involves the integration of additional optimization problems associated with the production line, such as logistics, layout design, and maintenance.

3.4. Line balancing and line design, logistics and/or maintenance, integration of assembly and disassembly operations

Aguilar et al. (2024) investigate the Parallel ALBP (PALBP) with a novel focus on multi-line workstations, heterogeneous cycle times across lines, and integrated buffer sizing. In scenarios where lines operate with different cycle times, multi-line workstations must produce in batches, necessitating the inclusion of buffers to manage synchronization. To tackle the bi-objective nature of the problem—minimizing both the number of workstations and the total buffer size—several multi-objective heuristics and metaheuristics are developed.

Battaïa et al. (2024) address the design of machining systems by jointly considering equipment selection and line balancing decisions to minimize total system cost. The proposed flow line incorporates multi-positional machines equipped with rotary tables, enabling the use of both vertical and horizontal machining modules for task execution. To solve this complex production optimization problem, a novel MILP model is developed, complemented by a heuristic algorithm designed to provide high-quality approximate solutions.

Schmid et al. (2024) simultaneously consider line balancing, assembly line feeding policies and facility sizing decisions within a unified framework. The resulting large-scale optimization problem is formulated using mathematical programming and addressed through a logic-based Benders' decomposition approach. Additionally, the study examines the impact of restricting the range of feeding policies on the complexity and cost of material flows within the facility. A key finding is the unexpectedly critical role of boxed-supply feeding, which emerges as essential for maintaining feasibility and minimizing total costs.

Zangaro et al. (2023) consider line balancing and feeding problem within multi-manned assembly stations. The authors propose a MILP model and a heuristic based on the Adaptive

Large Neighborhood Search framework, accommodating multiple workplaces per station and three feeding policies: line stocking, travelling kitting, and sequencing. The objective is to minimize the total cost of the assembly system, including supermarket, transportation, assembly, and investment costs. Although the integrated approach requires greater computational effort, it achieves significantly lower total costs compared to the sequential solution method.

Meng et al. (2023) integrate the predictive maintenance in the mixed-model assembly line balancing and sequencing problem. A mixed-integer linear programming model is proposed to minimize makespan and task alteration. A migrating birds optimization algorithm is developed to obtain Pareto frontier solutions and tested on a real-world case.

Zeng et al. (2025d) address the integrated optimization of conventional and preventive maintenance disassembly scenarios within a robotic disassembly line. They propose a MILP model that accounts for preventive maintenance tasks while aiming to enhance disassembly efficiency across both operational scenarios and improve the transition efficiency between them. The model incorporates realistic features such as tool replacement operations before and after tasks, reflecting practical disassembly conditions more accurately. To effectively solve large-scale instances, the authors develop a multi-objective genetic simulated annealing algorithm tailored to the problem's characteristics.

Zhang et al. (2023) propose a multi-objective hybrid evolutionary search algorithm designed to simultaneously optimise the number of workstations, idle index, and the quantity of production equipment required for the parallel production line balancing problem, which includes both disassembly and assembly tasks. The algorithm incorporates both crossover and mutation operations to generate neighbourhood individuals within the current evolutionary population. The mathematical model and algorithm are applied to a parallel production line specifically designed for the bogie remanufacturing production line of a railway freight car maintenance company.

Sun et al. (2024) address a multi-objective hybrid production line balancing problem with a fixed number of workstations incorporating both disassembly and assembly processes to simultaneously optimise cycle time, total cost, and workload smoothness. To solve this complex problem, the authors propose a novel Pareto-based hybrid genetic simulated annealing algorithm.

Contribution of the Special Issue:

Beldar et al. (2025) conduct a systematic literature review of Transfer LBP often relation to the equipment selection and line design. The primary objective was to classify the existing body of research. A novel classification framework based on tuple notation is proposed to organize the literature according to system configurations, problem characteristics, and optimization objectives. This structured framework not only synthesizes the current state of knowledge but also facilitates the identification of unexplored areas and emerging opportunities.

Telemeci and Azizoğlu (2024) study the transfer line balancing problem of type 2 and develop a new branch and bound.

Lu et al. (2024) developed an approach to integrate the design and verification of metal forming processes. The multi-architecture modelling language KARMA is employed to develop both meta-models and architecture models of the metal forming process, capturing multiple perspectives including mission, operations, functional behaviour, logical flow, and physical structure. Hervouet et al. (2025) introduce a methodology for the AS-IS representation of disassembly system design and implementation. The authors propose a strategic-level framework and validate it through a case study involving a Norwegian electronics manufacturer. Troncoso et al. (2024) investigate the product–mold–machine manufacturing problem, which arises in production environments such as tire, plastic, ceramic, and glass industries. The objective is to develop a production strategy that minimizes the total time required to fulfill product demand, subject to constraints such as limited machine and mold availability, changeover times, and mold-machine incompatibilities. The authors propose two MILP models alongside two polynomial-time constructive heuristics.

Mumtaz et al. (2024) study the optimisation problem that jointly addresses assembly line balancing and AGV scheduling for printed circuit board (PCB) assembly line. A MILP model is developed and implemented within an existing intelligent manufacturing platform used in a real-world PCB production environment. This platform comprises three layers: a physical layer, a data management layer, and an application service layer. A Genetic Artificial Bee Colony (GABC) algorithm is also proposed and embedded within the application service layer.

Kose et al. (2024) address a novel problem of evaluating disassembly line layout types using a comprehensive hierarchy of quantitative and qualitative criteria. The problem is formulated as a multi-criteria decision-making task. To solve it, a novel methodology is proposed that integrates Stepwise Weight Assessment Ratio Analysis and Weighted Aggregated Sum Product Assessment within a Fermatean fuzzy environment for sustainable waste management. The Fermatean fuzzy SWARA method is used to determine the weights of evaluation criteria, which include disassembly line balancing characteristics, reconfigurability, working conditions, and end-of-life (EOL) product features. These weights are then used in the Fermatean fuzzy WASPAS method to rank alternative disassembly line layouts—namely, straight, U-shaped, two-sided, and parallel layouts. A multi-objective MILP model is integrated to evaluate the disassembly line balancing performance of each layout, incorporating objectives such as minimizing the number of stations, prioritizing early removal of hazardous and high-demand parts, and reducing lead time. Qualitative criteria derived from expert opinions, such as reconfigurability and ergonomic considerations, are also incorporated. The proposed approach is validated through an application to a refrigerator disassembly line.

The next considered avenue of complexification involves the integration of supply chain management optimization problems, such as transportation and network design.

3.5 Line balancing integrated in Supply Chain

Çil et al. (2023) introduce an integrated distributed disassembly line balancing and vehicle routing problem. The authors develop a suite of solution methodologies, including MILP, mixed-integer non-linear programming (MINLP), and CP models as well as a multi-start simulated annealing algorithm.

Feng and Che (2023) critically examine the integrated disassembly line balancing and routing problem previously addressed by Diri Kenger et al. (2020). They demonstrate that the two MILP models presented in the original study can be decomposed into two independent subproblems, whose optimal solutions can be combined to derive the optimal solution of the original problem. Furthermore, they show that the three MINLP models can be reformulated as equivalent MILP models using two alternative linearisation techniques. Computational experiments reveal that the linearised models generally outperform the original nonlinear formulations in terms of solution quality and computational efficiency.

Durmaz and Budak (2025) study the integrated partial DLBP with a multi-objective green vehicle routing problem. The integrated problem is formulated as a multi-objective MILP model, with the dual objectives of minimizing total CO₂ emissions and overall cost. The Pareto-optimal solution set is obtained using the Augmented ε -Constraint Method. The model simultaneously determines (i) the number of workstations to be opened at the disassembly center, (ii) the optimal assignment of tasks to workstations and identification of non-disassembled tasks, (iii) the total and idle times at each workstation, and (iv) optimal vehicle routing strategies. To select the most suitable Pareto-optimal solution for both homogeneous and heterogeneous vehicle fleets, a multi-criteria decision-making framework combining the Entropy Weight Method and the Complex Proportional Assessment method is applied.

Habibi et al. (2024) consider an integrated Production-Routing Problem with Pickup and Delivery that minimizes the total cost associated with manufacturing, remanufacturing, disassembly, inventory, and transportation, while explicitly considering the remanufacturing and disassembly of end-of-life (EOL) returned products. To efficiently solve the problem, innovative hybrid heuristics—combining Two-Phase Iterative and Relax-and-Fix approaches—are developed and demonstrate superior performance compared to the Branch-and-Cut algorithm for large-scale instances with limited vehicle capacity.

Hu et al. (2023) investigate a novel integrated reverse supply chain design and DLBP for handling multiple EOL products, where the supply of EOL products, component demand, and disassembly task times are all subject to uncertainty. The problem simultaneously addresses decisions regarding the number and locations of disassembly facilities, equipment procurement, line balancing, and inventory levels for both collected EOL products and recovered components. A bi-objective two-stage stochastic programming model is proposed to maximize expected profit while minimizing carbon emissions. To solve the problem, an exact ε -constrained method is employed to convert the bi-objective model into a series of

single-objective problems. An enhanced Benders decomposition algorithm is developed to efficiently solve these formulations.

The integration of multiple optimization problems often necessitates the use of multi-objective formulations, as previously discussed. The growing prevalence of multi-objective optimization reflects the increasing complexity of modern production systems. In the following section, we highlight several solution methods employed to address conflicting objectives within this context.

Contribution of the Special Issue:

Tasoglu and Ilgin (2024) propose a simulation-based GA for the integrated optimization of reverse logistics network design, disassembly line balancing, and disassembly sequencing. The simulation model accounts for stochastic factors such as transportation and disassembly times, thereby capturing real-world variability.

4 Multi-objective optimisation

Zhou et al. (2022) address the DLBP with two objectives: minimizing the number of workstations required and minimizing operating costs. The authors formulate the problem as a multi-objective dynamic programming model and prove the monotonicity property of both objective functions. A backward recursive algorithm is developed to efficiently generate all non-dominated solutions.

Yetkin and Kahya (2022) address the integration of ergonomics into assembly line design by formulating a bi-objective mathematical model that simultaneously minimizes station time and the deviation of ergonomic risk scores across stations. To solve the bi-objective problem, the authors apply weighted sum and conic scalarization methods.

Lopes et al. (2023) focus on constructing Pareto fronts that explore trade-offs between cycle time and line length while balancing and sequencing paced systems. An industrial case study demonstrates that in paced lines, line length can function as a form of continuously distributable buffer capacity. This leads to a pattern of diminishing returns that is less pronounced than in unpaced systems. Consequently, the findings suggest that paced lines are more efficient, particularly when targeting lower cycle times.

Liang et al. (2023a) investigate the multi-parallel partial DLBP (MPPDLBP), considering four optimisation objectives: the number of shared workstations, workstation load balancing index, energy consumption, and profit. To address this complex problem, a MINLP model is developed alongside with hybrid genetic and tabu search algorithm.

Liang et al. (2023b) develop a MINLP model for a multi-objective partial DLBP, aiming to minimize four objectives: the number of workstations, workstation load, number of tool switches, and energy consumption. To capture the energy impact of tool switching, an energy consumption matrix is introduced. A multi-objective Improved Social Spider Algorithm is proposed to solve the problem.

Tian et al. (2024) develop a model for the DLBP with the objectives of minimising idle rates, enhancing line smoothness, reducing energy consumption, and balancing operator workloads under multiple constraints. Given the NP-hard nature of the problem, a hybrid intelligent algorithm combining simulated annealing and the water cycle algorithm is proposed to efficiently solve real-world disassembly cases. To address the challenge of selecting among multiple non-dominated solutions in multi-objective optimisation, the study adopts an “optimisation before decision-making” strategy. This involves integrating multi-criteria decision-making techniques with a neural network optimised using a particle swarm optimisation algorithm to identify the most satisfactory solution.

Contribution of the Special Issue:

Wang et al. (2023) study DLBP with partial destructive disassembly. A MILP model is formulated to simultaneously minimize the number of workstations, smoothness index, and energy consumption, while maximizing disassembly profit and a multi-objective GA is proposed. Ehm (2024), Multi-objective optimization was only studied by Kose et al. (2024,) Leite et al. (2024), Li et al. (2024b), Liu et al. (2024), Nourmohammadi et al. (2024,2025), Şahin and Kellegöz (2024), Zacharia et al. (2024), Zeng et al. (2023).

Multi-objective optimization is closely aligned with a global imperative that extends beyond manufacturing: the pursuit of sustainability in human activities. Sustainability is typically defined through three interrelated dimensions—economic, environmental, and social. While the discussion thus far has primarily focused on economic objectives, the following section explores how the environmental and social dimensions have been incorporated into assembly line balancing research.

A recent review on multi-objective disassembly line balancing and related supply chain management problems under uncertainty was presented by He et al. (2024a).

5 Sustainability considerations

The concept of sustainability is grounded in the triple bottom line framework, which encompasses economic, social, and environmental dimensions. In recent years, growing attention has been directed toward integrating these dimensions into production systems. In the context of assembly lines, social sustainability is typically associated with the use of manual labor, focusing on worker well-being and ergonomics, while environmental sustainability concerns are primarily linked to energy consumption, carbon emissions, and the generation of both hazardous and non-hazardous waste.

1.1. Social dimension

Recent advancements in technologies have reinvigorated interest in integrating ergonomics into the design and optimization of human-centered assembly systems driven by the concept of Industry 5.0, reflecting the growing awareness of worker well-being and the complexity of modern production environments. Faccio et al. (2023) discuss the consideration of human factors in production systems in cobot era in their recent review.

Rezvanizadeh et al. (2023) propose a comprehensive ergonomic index model that encompasses physical, cognitive, and environmental components. Using expert input and analytical hierarchy processes, they offer a validated framework capable of guiding ergonomic risk assessment and control strategies across diverse occupational contexts.

Digital twin technology is another promising avenue, as demonstrated by Caterino et al. (2023), who propose a simulation-based framework for evaluating ergonomic risks in complex, manual assembly systems. Their case study on car assembly highlights how job rotation strategies, informed by simulations, can significantly influence ergonomic outcomes.

Slama et al. (2024) emphasize the enduring relevance of manual labor in modern manufacturing and explore the application of emerging technologies—such as motion capture (MOCAP) and virtual reality (VR)—to enhance both system efficiency and worker well-being. Their study highlights the need to balance economic and human factors in assembly performance, proposing metrics for ergonomic risk and productivity based on human-centered technologies and operational research models.

Tropschuh et al. (2024) explore the increasing strain placed on an aging workforce and propose a four-step methodology for incorporating physiological and mental health criteria into employee scheduling systems. This approach fosters collaboration between ergonomics specialists and production planners, offering a more human-centered scheduling process. A practical example from a manual assembly line is used to illustrate how these adjustments can be operationalized to reduce fatigue, errors, and long-term health issues.

Tuo et al. (2024) propose a multimanned DLBP with walking workers. They investigate the fatigue attribute of workers during disassembly, introducing a novel evaluation index for muscle fatigue. The value of this attribute is assessed using the Analytical Hierarchy Process method. A mathematical model is developed with the goal of minimizing the number of workstations, workers, and worker fatigue indicators. A salp swarm algorithm with differential evolution algorithm is developed to solve the problem.

Possan Junior et al. (2023) studied the ErgoSALBP and developed a MILP model that incorporates the Occupational Repetitive Action index directly into ALBPs. Their lexicographic solution approach achieves an impressive 94% optimality rate across 2,160 instances, with 87% of solutions achieving ideal ergonomic conditions.

Guo et al. (2024) integrate destructive operation into the human-robot disassembly line while considering noise. First, a MIP model is established for human-robot hybrid partial destructive DLBP to accurately obtain the number of stations, smoothness index, costs and negative impact of noise pollution on workers. Then, an improved grey wolf optimization algorithm is proposed for the NP-hard characteristic of problem. A three-layer encoding and two-stage decoding strategy is designed to constrain the uniqueness of the solution, considering the noise constraints, and the different disassembly times of the human-robot. A disturbance factor is also designed to prevent local optimality, which enhances the performance of the proposed algorithm.

Abdous et al. (2023) study the interdependent decisions of workload balancing and equipment assignment. To address this challenge, a multi-objective optimization approach is proposed, aiming to minimize both investment costs and ergonomic impact, the latter evaluated through a fatigue and recovery-based criterion. The fatigue and recovery model is linearized to enable the formulation of a new MILP model. An exact solution method based on the ϵ -constraint approach is developed to generate Pareto-optimal trade-offs between cost and ergonomic performance.

Katiraei et al. (2023) introduce a comprehensive methodological framework for the assembly line worker assignment and rebalancing problem, which incorporates several practical considerations: performance-based worker assignment, integration of worker-dependent physical exertion constraints, and the use of experienced trainers to support less experienced operators. A bi-objective model is developed to simultaneously minimize the cycle time and the number of task reassignments, thereby preserving the original line design while integrating workers with diverse characteristics. The ϵ -constraint method is employed to generate Pareto frontiers for this bi-objective formulation.

Tiacci (2024a) presents a GA combined with discrete event simulation to assign rest times during line balancing rather than post hoc. By embedding ergonomic considerations—again using the OCRA index—into the balancing process, the proposed method enhances solution quality across benchmark instances, particularly when task ergonomic loads are high. This integrated approach supports profitability while maintaining worker health, offering a pragmatic path forward for ergonomic-conscious production design.

Giridhar et al. (2024) address this challenge through a multi-objective ALBP model aimed at minimizing the number of workstations, overall skill level requirements, and variance in workers' energy expenditure. To solve this complex problem, the authors employ two metaheuristic techniques—Non-Dominated Sorting GA II (NSGA-II) and Multi-Objective Simulated Annealing (MOSA)—within a Pareto optimality framework.

Abdous et al. (2025) integrate ergonomic considerations and variability in task execution times and propose a scenario-based optimization model that incorporates fatigue and recovery assessments to mitigate musculoskeletal disorder (MSD) risks. Their approach captures variability through probabilistic scenarios of operation times and applies an ILP model, solved via an Iterative Dichotomic Search algorithm. To evaluate the robustness of the model and inform dynamic managerial decisions—such as job rotation, overrun allowances, and scheduled rest breaks—a simulation framework is developed. Results from numerical experiments demonstrate that the model improves ergonomic outcomes without compromising production efficiency. Specifically, it reduces worker fatigue, supports more equitable task allocation, and enables managers to proactively implement policies that prevent long-term health issues.

In contrast, Alfaro-Pozo and Bautista-Valhondo (2024) examine the trade-offs between ergonomic design and production efficiency, presenting a more critical view of ergonomic

integration. By introducing a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) model that accounts for ergonomic risk, spatial constraints, and task times, they analyze the cost implications of designing safer assembly lines. Their results highlight that while ergonomic improvements can significantly reduce worker risk, they often come at the cost of increased idle time and additional workstations. For instance, maintaining moderate ergonomic risk levels in an engine assembly case study resulted in a maximum daily production drop of 27 engines, underlining the tension between safety and throughput.

Contribution of the Special Issue:

Keshvarparast et al. (2024) propose a novel mathematical model aimed at accelerating the ergonomic design of human–robot collaborative workstations. The model is based on task alternatives and incorporates integrated assessments of postural risk and muscle fatigue for each task, with the goal of creating an ergonomically optimized collaborative environment. The evaluation framework combines surface electromyography and postural risk assessment using inertial measurement units, implemented through a digital ergonomic platform. This setup enables the determination of optimal workstation configurations—including the placement of tools, equipment, and human–robot interactions—that enhance physical well-being while maintaining station productivity.

Leite et al. (2024) study a job rotation model for production cells in the footwear industry—specifically in the manufacturing of sandals and tennis shoes—with the aim of reducing workers’ exposure to risks associated with work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WMSDs). The model integrates both physical and psychological workload assessments into a multi-objective optimization framework. Physical workload was evaluated using the Occupational Repetitive Actions (OCRA) method, while psychological workload was measured using the Job Stress Scale. The mathematical model simultaneously seeks to minimize the maximum risk of WMSDs and the overall work demand, while maximizing the minimum levels of job control and social support experienced by workers during their shifts.

1.2. Environmental impact

Zeng et al. (2022) present a multi-objective model for robotic disassembly line balancing and sequencing, aiming to minimize disassembly completion time while maximizing energy efficiency and profit. To solve the problem effectively, an improved genetic simulated annealing algorithm is developed, tailored to the specific characteristics of the disassembly process.

Lahrichi et al. (2025) address a bi-objective Robotic ALBP that simultaneously minimizes cycle time and energy consumption. The considered energy model accounts for consumption during both active operation and idle periods. A pseudo-polynomial case is addressed using an exact algorithm known as *split*, which enumerates all Pareto-optimal solutions for a given global (giant) task sequence. This exact method is employed as a decoder within a metaheuristic framework that explores a reduced solution space where giant sequences serve as the encoding mechanism.

Kubilay et al. (2024) propose CP models for addressing the Parallel ALBP (PALBP) and the Parallel Robotic ALBP (PRALBP). Extensive computational experiments demonstrate that the CP model outperforms existing approaches by improving the best-known results for the majority of benchmark instances related to PRALBP. The authors also introduce an energy-efficient variant of PRALBP (E-PRALBP), incorporating both cycle time and energy consumption as performance criteria. Furthermore, an extended version, E-PRALBP with zoning constraints and a limited number of robots (E-PRALBP-Z), is also formulated.

Soysal-Kurt et al. (2025) investigate E-PRALBP in the Mixed-Model mode where both line balancing and model sequencing (MPRALB/S) are solved to optimize simultaneously cycle time and energy consumption. A modified Non-Dominated Sorting GA II (MNSGA-II) is proposed and tested on newly generated instances. MNSGA-II is compared with standard NSGA-II and a restarted Simulated Annealing algorithm using widely accepted performance indicators: hypervolume ratio, the ratio of non-dominated solutions, and generational distance.

Contribution of the Special Issue:

Petersen et al. (2025) present a comprehensive literature review of LBPs with a specific focus on energy efficiency. The quantitative analysis identifies dominant patterns and emerging trends in energy-efficient line balancing, while the qualitative component examines line configurations, managerial factors, optimization objectives, solution methods, and practical implementations.

Ehm (2024) address selective disassembly planning and scheduling for multiple products within a dismantling shop, with a specific focus on the environmental impacts arising during the process planning stage. It extends existing models by introducing flexible disassembly levels and modes. The proposed multi-objective optimization problem seeks to balance time efficiency, ecological impacts from process-related emissions, and penalties associated with the recovery of damaged components, unseparated assemblies, or unrefined materials. A formal mathematical model is developed and illustrated through a case study involving EOL engine disassembly. A multi-objective GA is designed.

Nourmohammadi et al. (2024, 2025) consider robot energy consumption in their composite cost function. Zeng et al. (2023) use the reduction of energy consumption as one of objective functions for the design of disassembly lines.

Güler et al. (2024) presents a comprehensive review on Partial DLBP providing valuable insights into the evolution of PDLB approaches and highlighting opportunities for future exploration to support circular economy objectives.

6 Uncertainty management and reconfigurable manufacturing systems

In practical applications, decision-makers often lack precise information regarding product specifications, customer demand, workforce capabilities, and manufacturing processes during the initial stages of assembly line balancing. To address this inherent uncertainty,

various methodological approaches have been proposed in the literature, aiming to incorporate data variability into the balancing process: stochastic modelling, fuzzy programming, simulation and stability theory.

6.1. Stochastic processing times and uncertainty of demand

Two new branch and bound algorithms were proposed for the stochastic ALBP, where task processing times are stochastic and cycle time constraints must be satisfied with a probability.

Diefenbach and Stolletz (2022) introduce a reliability-based branch-and-bound (RB&B) algorithm designed to ensure a minimum number of stations while satisfying a target line reliability—the probability that all tasks can be completed within the cycle time. The authors propose a sampling-based formulation and prove that any lower bound from the deterministic version of the problem can be transformed into a valid bound for the stochastic setting. These bounds can be integrated into various optimization frameworks, including MIP solvers and heuristic algorithms. The RB&B algorithm explicitly models interdependencies between stations, accounting for reliability constraints across the full line. Advanced fathoming strategies based on transformed bounds and reliability measures help to reduce computation times.

Li et al. (2024b) propose a branch, bound, and remember (BBR) algorithm to solve the chance-constrained stochastic ALBP (SALBP), where task processing times are stochastic and cycle time constraints must be satisfied with a predefined probability. The BBR approach employs a cyclic best-first search strategy and stores all explored partial solutions in memory, enabling rapid identification of high-quality complete solutions. To enhance computational efficiency, the authors introduce new lower bounds and dominance rules specifically adapted for stochastic task durations. A comprehensive experimental study, involving 1,614 benchmark instances, demonstrates the method's superior performance. Compared to two MIP models and twenty re-implemented heuristic and metaheuristic algorithms—including GAs, ant colony optimization, and simulated annealing—the BBR algorithm consistently achieves better solution quality, particularly for large instances.

Şahin and Tural (2023) investigate the Robotic Stochastic ALBP where human workers and robots operate at separate workstations. Task processing times are modelled as normally distributed, with parameters varying according to the type of operator—robots being characterized by significantly lower (potentially negligible) variability compared to human workers. It is assumed that human workers are fully capable while robots are able to perform a subset of the tasks. The authors focus on the minimization of the cycle time for a given a fixed number of workstations and robots, under stochastic task times. The study proposes two mathematical formulations: a Mixed-Integer Second-Order Cone Programming model and a CP model.

He et al. (2022) address an integrated stochastic disassembly line balancing and planning problem aimed at minimizing total system cost under uncertainty in component yield ratios and product demand. The model incorporates machine-specific characteristics, including

cost, capabilities, and processing capacity. A two-stage non-linear stochastic programming model is initially formulated and subsequently linearized to improve tractability. To enhance computational efficiency, a valid inequality is introduced based on a structural analysis of the problem, effectively reducing the search space. Two solution approaches are employed: Sample Average Approximation (SAA) and an L-shaped decomposition algorithm.

Li et al. (2023) investigate the joint optimization of the ALBP and the capacitated lot-sizing problem. The problem is modelled as a two-stage stochastic program assuming a risk-averse decision maker. To address the computational challenges of the model, efficient solution procedures are developed. A case study focused on mask production, motivated by the disruptions observed during the COVID-19 pandemic, is presented to demonstrate the applicability of the approach.

Mete et al. (2023) develop a GA and a constructive heuristic based on Dijkstra's algorithm for solving the DLBP under stochastic task durations. The performance of the proposed algorithms is evaluated using benchmark instances and compared against a piecewise-linear model (PLM) and simulated annealing (SA). Results show that the GA consistently outperforms the other methods across all test instances in terms of the average relative percentage deviation in the number of workstations. Furthermore, the Dijkstra-based heuristic demonstrates superior performance compared to both PLM and SA, with respect to both the number of workstations and computational time.

Guo et al. (2022) study a stochastic multi-product multi-objective disassembly-sequencing-line-balancing problem aiming at maximizing disassembly profit and minimizing energy consumption and carbon emission. A simulated annealing and multi-objective discrete grey wolf optimizer with a stochastic simulation approach is proposed.

Contribution of the Special Issue:

Liu et al. (2024) propose an evaluation method for estimating remanufacturing assembly time that employs the Fuzzy Graphical Evaluation and Review Technique network to predict the expected assembly time for each operation.

Simulation approaches.

Simulation-based approaches have also proven valuable in evaluating assembly line performance under stochastic conditions.

Moncayo et al. (2025) propose a hybrid methodology combining deterministic optimization and simulation-based optimization to address uncertainty in real-world ALBPs. Initially, a deterministic model minimizes cycle time, after which simulation is used to assess the impact of stochastic factors such as processing times, inter-arrival times, number of workers, and material handling speed. Finally, simulation-based optimization is applied to refine parameter values, ensuring the average cycle time remains close to the deterministic target. Applied to a motorcycle assembly line, the method demonstrates robust performance.

Stade et al. (2024) focus on robotic assembly line balancing under uncertain process times caused by feedback control systems compensating for disturbances in car body construction. The authors present a simulation framework that incorporates empirical process time distributions, enabling more accurate evaluation of cycle time risks. By repeatedly sampling from actual production data and comparing it with results derived from normally distributed assumptions, the study demonstrates that using empirical distributions significantly reduces the frequency and severity of cycle time underestimations, improving planning reliability for robotic lines.

Wu et al. (2024) formulate a simulation optimization problem for mixed-model two-sided assembly lines, where task processing times are uncertain. The primary objective is to minimize the expected cycle time, which represents the average time required to complete a product on the assembly line. A decomposition approach is introduced, dividing the core problem into two distinct sub-tasks: task allocation to workstations and determination of task sequences at each station. Building on this framework, a novel simulation-optimization algorithm, called the Decomposition Approach with Harmony Search (DAHS), is developed.

Jung et al. (2022) apply simulation techniques in the labor-intensive garment industry by integrating for task time estimation the power consumption data from sewing machines, collected via ICT-based monitoring systems, which are processed in real time and converted into task durations using approximation algorithms. These inputs feed a discrete-event simulation model used to evaluate production line performance. Compared to traditional estimation methods, the simulation results showed an 18.8% increase in accuracy, underscoring the effectiveness of data-driven simulation approaches in enhancing productivity and operational transparency.

Al-Fandi and Almasarwah (2025) investigate human-robot cooperation in a two-sided DLBP. A mathematical model is developed to optimize cycle time, followed by a simulation model that accounts for uncertainty arising from factors such as resource skill levels, the quality of EOL products, and the number of active workstations. Statistical analysis using design of experiments and ANOVA reveals that these factors, along with their interactions, significantly impact key performance indicators such as time in the system, cycle time, and average resource utilization. The composite desirability function of a response optimizer is then employed to identify the optimal factor levels that simultaneously minimize cycle time and time in the system, while maximizing average resource utilization under various operational conditions. The results demonstrate that the configuration with the shortest disassembly time consistently achieves the highest composite desirability across all cases. Although increasing the number of workstations reduces or maintains cycle time, this does not always yield proportional improvements in performance. A custom dashboard is developed to assist decision-makers in optimizing disassembly line performance for diverse EOL scenarios.

Torkul et al. (2024) evaluate the impact of line-to-seru conversion on environmental and economic performance metrics. The study introduces an integrated approach combining simulation and Data Envelopment Analysis. Simulation experiments are conducted using

various scenarios for circuit breaker production, comparing traditional assembly lines to seru production systems. Despite elevated training costs, the line-seru conversion is shown to offer substantial operational and environmental advantages.

Contribution of the Special Issue.

Tiacci (2024b) proposes a GA combined with discrete event simulation to simultaneously address Mixed-Model ALBP, buffer allocation between stations, and optimization of the model sequencing for asynchronous lines.

Zacharia et al. (2024) conduct simulation experiments to address the uncertainty inherent in manual task processing times by incorporating fuzziness into manual assembly lines with cobots. Schibelbain et al. (2024) use simulation for performance evaluation of the optimized mixed-model robotic assembly lines.

Tasoglu and Ilgin (2024) introduces a simulation-based GA to jointly optimize network design for reverse logistics, disassembly line balancing and disassembly sequencing. The simulation model incorporates stochastic elements such as transportation and disassembly durations, reflecting real-world uncertainties.

He et al. (2024b) investigate the integration of dynamic workload balancing into part input sequencing for comprehensive flexible manufacturing systems scheduling. An online algorithm is proposed to dynamically balance workloads, supported by a mathematical model that coordinates task scheduling across both machines and the robotic part-handling system on the shop floor. The approach is evaluated through simulation-based experiments and statistical analysis.

Salatiello et al. (2024) address scheduling challenges in production systems and propose two novel dispatching rules that leverage real-time system data to generate adaptive production schedules. They consider exponential and uniform distribution of processing times and use simulation experiments to analyse the system performances.

Stability radius.

Shibasaki et al. (2024) proposed an advanced upper-bounding method for the problem of maximizing the stability radius in simple assembly line designs under uncertainty in task processing times. This NP-hard optimization problem involves assigning tasks—subject to precedence constraints—to a fixed number of workstations with a fixed cycle time, with the goal of identifying a robust configuration that tolerates the largest increase in task durations while maintaining feasibility. The authors introduced a Dantzig-Wolfe decomposition combined with column generation to reformulate the problem, incorporating valid inequalities and tight assignment intervals to reduce the solution space of the pricing sub-problems. A bisection method is also applied as a preprocessing step to enhance the initial upper bound used in the column generation process.

Another strategy to address market volatility involves the implementation of Reconfigurable Manufacturing Systems (RMS), which are designed to adapt efficiently and cost-effectively to fluctuations in demand.

6.2. Design and balancing of Reconfigurable Manufacturing Systems

Hashemi-Petroodi et al. (2023) study reconfigurable mixed-model assembly line framework. In this setting, tasks can be dynamically reassigned to stations at each takt, workers are allowed to move between stations after each takt, and the sequence of incoming product models is considered infinite and unknown. Equipment assignment is performed during the line design phase, with the possibility of duplicating equipment across stations. The dynamic assignment of tasks and worker movements is modelled as a Markov Decision Process (MDP), which is then reformulated as a Linear Program (LP). The overall line design problem is framed as a MILP that integrates the MDP. To improve tractability, reduction rules and a decomposed transition process are developed. Stochastic and robust variants of the MILP are proposed to address uncertainty, with objectives focused on minimizing the expected total cost across all takts and the worst-case total cost, respectively. Computational experiments on benchmark and synthetic datasets validate the effectiveness of the proposed models. The results highlight the advantages of dynamic task assignment, demonstrating superior performance compared to fixed and model-dependent assignment strategies commonly found in the literature.

Delorme and Gianessi (2024) examine the potential of the reconfigurable parallel-serial manufacturing line with crossover for reducing peak electric power consumption. To solve the corresponding optimization problem, a time-indexed integer linear programming model is proposed, combining balancing and scheduling decisions, alongside a matheuristic approach tailored for large-scale instances. Computational experiments on a broad set of test cases demonstrate that significant power peak reductions—averaging 33%—can be achieved.

Yelles-Chaouche et al. (2022) address the optimization of reconfigurable production line design with a fixed number of workstations. The production lines under consideration are capable of processing multiple products, with reconfiguration achieved by reassigning tasks between workstations when switching between product types. Given a set of products and their production sequence, the objective is to determine a feasible line configuration for each product that minimizes the total number of task reassignments. Each configuration involves allocating tasks to workstations while satisfying cycle time and precedence constraints. To solve this problem, a MILP model is formulated. Additionally, a MILP-based heuristic, called Halt-and-Fix, is developed to efficiently handle large-scale instances. This model and heuristic are further adapted for the multi-model case by Tremblet et al. (2023). The multi-model assembly line is designed to produce various products in batches, each requiring a specific configuration. When the product type changes, the line must be reconfigured to meet updated task precedence and cycle time constraints. Reconfiguration involves reassigning tasks among existing workstations. The main objective is to determine a configuration for

each product that minimizes the maximum number of task reassignments, regardless of the sequence of product arrivals.

Albus and Huber (2023) present an IP-based optimization approach to address dynamic resource reconfiguration in automatic assembly lines. Their method is evaluated using a newly developed benchmark dataset that incorporates multi-cost resource constraints and reflects the characteristics of an existing production line. Results indicate that the proposed model reduces total assembly line costs by an average factor of 1.9 compared to an optimized greenfield solution. However, this cost reduction comes at the expense of a higher number of workstations and decreased line efficiency. Further, Albus et al. (2025) addresses the Robotic ALBP with Task Types, incorporating additional company-specific constraints, by introducing a problem-specific GA for line reconfiguration. Both greenfield (new design) and brownfield (existing system reconfiguration) scenarios are considered. In addition to a mathematical formulation, a GA is proposed.

Monguzzi et al. (2024) present a methodology for designing the architecture of a Reconfigurable Assembly System (RAS) that integrates both human operators and mobile robotic agents. The proposed approach addresses the assembly of multi-product, medium-to light-weight components that were originally assembled manually. The methodology systematically determines the optimal number of workstations, defines the specific set of operations to be performed at each station, and supports the design of a layout that ensures system reconfigurability. To formalize this approach, the authors introduce and define the concepts of operations, operation datasheets, assembly trees, and macro-operations. Additionally, the study provides guidelines for flexibly automating operations. The methodology is validated through a use case involving the assembly of various types of motorbike brakes, demonstrating the system's adaptability and reconfigurability.

Mezghani et al. (2024) explore the design of assembly lines that remain effective under product evolution throughout the line's lifecycle. As the evolution of the product family is unknown, the authors adopt a robust optimization approach. The study focuses on a mixed-model assembly line composed of stations, each equipped with a worker or robot and associated equipment. The line assembles various models within a product family, and reconfiguration is triggered when a new product model replaces an existing one. Reconfiguration involves reallocating tasks and rearranging resources and equipment. To address this challenge, a novel MILP model is proposed, aiming to minimize the total cost of the initial line design and all future reconfigurations, considering the worst-case scenario of product evolution. An adversarial optimization approach is developed to solve large-scale instances efficiently.

Kim et al. (2025) tackle the system-level configuration selection problem for Reconfigurable Single Part Flow Lines, characterized by parallel identical flexible machines at each processing stage. The objective is to determine the optimal number of stages, the number of machines per stage, and the assignment of operations to each stage to meet the demand for a single part type, while accounting for operation precedence constraints and spatial limitations. To

minimize the total cost—comprising machine purchase and operation processing costs—the authors develop a nonlinear IP model and Variable Neighbourhood Search (VNS) algorithm, which constructs an initial solution using a greedy heuristic and refines it through shaking and local search procedures. This algorithm is further enhanced by incorporating a Variable Neighbourhood Descent mechanism.

Battaia et al. (2023) address the problem of optimally configuring a rotary transfer machine with turrets for the machining of multiple parts. At the preliminary design stage, decisions must be made regarding the orientations of parts on the rotary table, the allocation of tasks to positions, the assignment of machining modules, and the selection of cutting modes for each spindle head and turret. The objective is to minimize the total equipment cost. To solve the problem, the authors develop an efficient heuristic framework to aid decision-makers in managing the production of multiple part batches.

Cui et al. (2025) develop a two-stage stochastic programming model to minimise configuration cost, reconfiguration cost, expected inventory and back-order cost for a RMS. To efficiently handle a large number of variables, a set-covering model is obtained by using Danzig-Wolfe (DW) decomposition along with its corresponding pricing subproblem. A solution algorithm is based on the column generation framework. To further improve the algorithm performance for larger instances, a column selection method is introduced to identify additional columns that have the potential to reduce the objective function value of the integer solution during the column generation iterations. These columns are then added to the set-covering model. The process of column selection is accelerated by employing the Graph Neural Network (GNN) algorithm. Furthermore, GNN trained on data from small instances can be directly applied to larger instances as well.

Delorme et al. (2023) formulate a bi-level optimization problem, where the line balancing of the RMS represents the upper level, and the configuration planning forms the lower level. The optimization considers three key criteria: the number of workstations, the expected service level, and the expected energy cost, while accounting for demand uncertainty through scenario analysis. A three-phase metaheuristic is developed, and its performance is evaluated using instances derived from existing literature.

Ostovari et al. (2025) present a novel multi-objective IP model designed to optimize the configuration and capacity scalability of reconfigurable machine tools in uncertain environments. The model targets the minimization of three key objectives: total energy consumption, unused capacity, and total cost. It also incorporates critical manufacturing constraints, such as peak power thresholds and limited tool availability. To address fluctuations in demand, a scenario-based robust optimization approach is employed, balancing the need for solution robustness with model adaptability. A comprehensive case study is conducted to demonstrate the model's effectiveness, comparing solutions under deterministic and uncertain conditions. Sensitivity analyses are performed on parameters such as peak power thresholds, risk coefficients, and infeasibility weights, highlighting their influence on system performance.

Ameer and Dahane (2023) propose a novel methodology that simultaneously considers setup and process planning constraints in manufacturing systems. By examining the interdependencies among operations, an integrated plan is developed to minimize the total cost, encompassing processing, tolerance, setup change, and tool module costs. The approach follows a two-stage hybrid GA framework. In the first stage, a heuristic is used to generate setup configurations and assign fixtures to operation groups. In the second stage, a GA identifies the optimal process plan corresponding to the generated setup, aiming to minimize economic costs.

Cerqueus and Delorme (2023) study the design-for-scalability problem in RMS. The proposed measure adopts a multi-objective framework to assess the scalability of single-product manufacturing systems by analyzing the complete range of feasible system configurations. Numerical experiments are conducted to compare the proposed indicator with an existing scalability measure and conventional production line design metrics.

Vahedi-Nouri et al. (2023) present the first study to address the integrated production scheduling and workforce planning problem in RMS that leverage reconfigurable machines and human–robot collaboration. The authors formulate the problem using a novel MILP and CP models, with the objective of minimizing the makespan. Results show that the CP model significantly outperforms the MILP model in small- and medium-sized instances and is capable of producing high-quality solutions for larger instances within practical time limits.

Li et al. (2022) address the assembly line rebalancing problem by proposing two distinct strategies: a periodic rebalancing policy and a data-driven rebalancing policy. The objective is to minimize the total cost, which encompasses both production and rebalancing costs. An empirical study is conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of these approaches. The proposed data-driven policy outperforms the conventional multiperiod policy, offering more efficient and cost-effective rebalancing decisions.

Contributions of the Special Issue:

Karas Celik and Ozcelik (2025) introduce the Assembly Line Rebalancing Problem with Human–Robot Collaboration. The problem focuses on rebalancing existing manual assembly lines to accommodate both traditional and collaborative robots as operators. A mathematical programming model and a hyper-heuristic algorithm based on the Artificial Bee Colony algorithm are proposed, with the primary objective of minimizing cycle time.

Yelles-Chaouche et al. (2024) address the design and balancing problem of a modular multi-product RMS. The system under consideration consists of a fixed number of modular machines arranged linearly and interconnected by a material handling system, with each machine accommodating a limited number of module slots. The line is designed to process multiple product types in batch mode, where each batch necessitates a specific reconfiguration of the line. The primary objective is to determine the minimal number of modules and their optimal arrangement across configurations required to manufacture all

product types. To address this problem, an ILP model is developed as well as a decomposition strategy and an associated heuristic algorithm.

6.3. Task failures

Guo et al. (2023) investigate a stochastic DLBP that accounts for task failure risks, aiming to maximize the expected recovery profit. The study begins with the development of a mathematical model that incorporates task failure probabilities into the profit maximization objective. To efficiently solve the problem, the authors propose a hybrid metaheuristic algorithm that combines a variable neighbourhood descent method with an artificial bee colony algorithm. The proposed approach is evaluated through three case studies.

Singh et al. (2023) address task failure scenarios in disassembly lines using a predictive–reactive approach that initially relaxes the cycle time constraint. This relaxation disrupts the paced operation of the disassembly line, leading to workflow congestion or blockages at downstream stations. To overcome this, the authors propose a station crashing-based recursive solution method, accompanied by a mathematical model that resolves task failures without relaxing the cycle time constraint. The objective is to maximize disassembly line profit while minimizing the number of workstations needed to implement corrective actions. The effectiveness of the proposed approach is illustrated through a case study involving the disassembly of a toy car.

Goksoy Kalaycilar et al. (2022) investigate an ALBP that incorporates hazardous tasks with uncertain success rates. Failures in such tasks can propagate damage within the current workstation and across subsequent stations, amplifying operational risks. To address this, the authors develop a two-stage stochastic MIP model aimed at maximizing the expected net revenue. Task-to-workstation assignments are determined in the first stage, before the uncertainty regarding task outcomes is realized. The model is initially presented for cases involving one to three hazardous tasks and is then generalized to handle any number. Computational experiments reveal that the performance is highly sensitive to the number and success probabilities of hazardous tasks.

Zhang et al. (2025) investigate the integration of destructive disassembly into multi-robot and multi-product disassembly systems, incorporating component failure and hazard characteristics under realistic resource constraints. The study formulates a MILP model with the objective of optimising cycle time, total energy consumption, peak energy demand, and disassembly profit. To efficiently solve this complex problem, the authors propose an improved multi-objective water cycle algorithm featuring a four-layer encoding structure and a sequential crossover mechanism. The algorithm is benchmarked against 12 state-of-the-art multi-objective optimisation methods across four disassembly scenarios. Two real-world engine disassembly case studies further validate the proposed methodology.

Contributions of the Special Issue:

Goksoy Kalaycilar et al. (2024) study the DLBP under stochastic conditions, where a fixed number of workstations is considered and hazardous tasks may fail with known probabilities. Each hazardous task carries a risk of failure, and if a failure occurs, the disassembly line halts and all tasks assigned to downstream workstations are interrupted. The objective is to select and assign tasks to workstations in a way that maximizes the total expected net revenue. The authors develop a heuristic approach based on the linear programming relaxation of a recently proposed stochastic mixed-integer programming model (Goksoy Kalaycilar et al. 2022).

A prominent trend in the current literature is the increasing focus on human-robot collaboration. Several such contributions have been already mentioned in this paper.

7 Human-robot collaboration (HRC)

Ponnambalam et al. (2023) discuss the role and challenges of HRC in manufacturing and logistics. Petzoldt et al. (2023) methodically examine the aspect of task allocation for collaborative assembly through a systematic literature review. The paper presents the current state of the art in task allocation approaches, investigates the criteria for determining suitable task assignments, and discusses the challenges and future research directions in the field.

Wu et al. (2024a) introduce a novel HRC DLBP and propose a MILP model aimed at minimising the number of workstations, the smoothness index, and various associated costs. A hybrid local search GA is developed to solve the problem, incorporating a four-layer encoding and decoding strategy tailored to the problem's characteristics. The algorithm is applied to a power battery disassembly case.

Wu et al. (2024b) formulate a techno-economic and environmental profit-oriented HRC DLBP. A MIP model is developed with the objectives of minimizing the number of workstations and the smoothing index, and maximizing techno-economic and environmental benefits. To solve this problem efficiently, a multi-objective immune GA (MIGA) is introduced. It incorporates a five-layer encoding method and a triple decoding strategy based on the problem's characteristics, alongside immune operators integrated into the NSGA-II structure.

Mao et al. (2025) investigate the combination of the parallel ALBP (PALBP) with HRC where human workers and robots collaborate to execute tasks both in parallel and cooperatively. A MIP model is formulated to minimize cycle time, and a lower bound is proposed for the problem. The authors develop an adapted tabu search algorithm for the problem.

Faccio et al. (2024) present a model that incorporates safety as a constraint, aiming to both maximize productivity in a collaborative workcell and ensure secure HRC. The model uses indexes that take into account both process and product characteristics to evaluate its quality. The proposed model is compared to one without the safety constraint.

Kheirabadi et al. (2025) address the safety challenges in HRC within the context of an ALBP aimed at minimizing cycle time. They develop a CP-based model that optimally assigns cobots to workstations, allocates assembly tasks between humans and cobots, and sequences them

on a single-model line. The model introduces a novel workstation zoning policy designed to eliminate medium- and high-risk parallel tasks in collaborative workstations. A second version of the model is developed to minimize the number of cobots used.

Cai et al. (2025a) propose a new task allocation optimization model for HRC ALBP, aimed at minimizing cycle time, reducing workload variance across different workstations, and decreasing the assembly complexity per unit product. They develop an improved multi-objective migratory bird optimization algorithm with fast non-dominated sorting. Cai et al. (2025b) focus on optimizing the number of stations, makespan, and balance ratio in a HRC ALBP. They design an improved dual-population GA.

Huang et al. (2024) investigate the HRC in mixed-model two-sided ALBP. They formulate a MIP model with objectives to minimize ergonomic risk, energy consumption, and cycle time. They propose a multi-objective discrete artificial bee colony algorithm with specialist bees. This algorithm utilizes a novel five-vector encoding and decoding scheme, incorporating two types of neighbor structures for each vector. Additionally, specialist bees are introduced to search for optimal solutions for each objective, while a tabu list is employed to help escape local optima. The algorithm also incorporates variable neighborhood descent to enhance exploration capabilities and a temperature-based food sources update mechanism to probabilistically update the food sources of employed bees, reinforcing exploitation.

Sikora and Weckenborg (2023) propose three different decomposition approaches for Benders' decomposition algorithms for HRC ALBP exploring multiple possible partitions of the formulation variables.

Zheng et al. (2025) address the optimization of cycle time in HRC ALBP, focusing on heterogeneous collaborative robots and limited resources and formulate a CP model. They also develop an improved fruit fly optimization algorithm. This algorithm introduces two vectors for encoding: the task assignment vector, which addresses the task allocation sub-problem, and the process alternative vector, which handles the process alternative allocation sub-problem. The algorithm employs a decoding procedure integrated with CP to generate an optimal scheduling scheme for the stations involving both human workers and collaborative robots.

Mao et al. (2024) address the ALBP with multi-type cobots, enabling both humans and robots to perform tasks either in parallel or collaboration. They formulate a MIP model to minimize the cycle time and propose a tight lower bound for the problem. An adaptive neighbourhood simulated annealing algorithm is developed, featuring specifically designed neighbourhood operators and structures. It is further enhanced with an adaptive mechanism that dynamically adjusts the weights of the neighbourhood structures based on historical data.

Zeng et al. (2025b) formulate two MIP models to optimize cycle time in assembly lines featuring multi-type cobots, parallel collaboration, and a limited number of workers. The authors also develop two metaheuristics: an artificial bee colony algorithm and a migrating bird optimization algorithm. Both algorithms employ dual-vector encoding and use a

decoding procedure based on mathematical programming to derive feasible scheduling schemes.

Zheng et al. (2025c) investigate the ALBP involving cobots with an emphasis on ergonomic considerations. A mathematical model is formulated to minimize both the cycle time and the variation in ergonomic risks among human workers. A multi-objective restarted simulated annealing algorithm is also developed. The algorithm employs a three-vector encoding scheme: the task assignment vector addresses the task allocation sub-problem, the process alternative vector handles the assignment of alternative processes, and the task process alternative selection vector determines specific process selections. A decoding procedure translates these vectors into feasible solutions and evaluates the ergonomic risks at each station. Two enhancements are incorporated into the algorithm: (1) a novel multi-objective acceptance criterion for selecting new solutions, and (2) a restart mechanism that replaces the current solution with one selected from the permanent Pareto archive based on a modified crowding distance.

Keshvarparast et al. (2025) propose a mathematical model to optimise the performance of a HRC ALBP by minimising the cycle time. The model incorporates various collaboration scenarios—sequential, simultaneous, supportive, and their possible combinations—enabling flexible integration of human–robot interaction across the line. It also accounts for differences in workforce characteristics, such as individual skill levels and fatigue, allowing for the dynamic assignment of human workers and collaborative robots to stations based on their specific attributes.

Zhu et al. (2024) address the balancing of a HRC DLBP by formulating a MIP model that incorporates four optimisation objectives: minimising the number of workstations, balancing task operator idle time, and minimising both remanufacturing demand and hazard indices. A mapping constraint mechanism is introduced to allocate disassembly tasks to operators based on remanufacturing requirements and component hazard levels. A teaching–learning-based optimisation algorithm is proposed, featuring a two-layer encoding strategy tailored to the problem’s structure and an embedded perturbation strategy for enhanced solution quality.

Fang et al. (2024) address the position-constrained HRC disassembly planning problem, which encompasses three key subproblems: disassembly sequence planning, disassembly line balancing, and robot path planning. They develop a multi-objective MIP and a multi-fidelity optimisation algorithm.

Yin et al. (2023) investigate the impact of end-of-life states of waste products and skill differences among workers on the production efficiency and workload balance in partial DLBP. A MIP model is proposed to minimize cycle time and idle balancing index while maximizing disassembly profit, under the constraint of a fixed number of open workstations. A NSGA-II algorithm based on an incentive strategy is also developed.

Yin et al. (2025) design a multi-man–robot collaborative disassembly station and study the corresponding DLBP. A MIP model is formulated to minimize the number of stations, the

number of operators (both workers and robots), total disassembly time, and the idle balancing index. A genetic Jaya algorithm is proposed, combining the strengths of both the GA and the Jaya algorithm.

Contribution of the Special Issue:

Fathi et al. (2024) present a systematic review of assembly-line balancing research, specifically focusing on lines that incorporate industrial and collaborative robots. The reviewed studies are categorized by objective functions and analysed in terms of solution techniques, line configurations, and other critical parameters.

Kheirabadi et al. (2023) present a comprehensive review of state-of-the-art balancing problems in collaborative robotic assembly lines, with a focus on the past decade of research. In addition to balancing, the review highlights how resource selection, allocation, and scheduling are increasingly integrated into optimization models.

Nourmohammadi et al. (2024) address the integrated optimization of task allocation and station design in both straight and U-shaped assembly lines, considering multiple objectives: minimizing the number of stations (Type-1), minimizing cycle time (Type-2), and minimizing a composite cost function that includes station costs, operator costs, and robot energy consumption (Type-rw). The Type-rw objective reflects realistic manufacturing settings where diverse human and robotic agents, with varying skills and energy requirements, collaborate or operate in parallel at workstations. In addition, this model incorporates practical constraints such as robot tool changeovers, zoning limitations, and specific technological requirements relevant to real-world production environments. Several MILP models are developed with tailored upper and lower bounds to improve computational efficiency. Further, Nourmohammadi et al. (2025) propose a set of constraint programming (CP) models for the considered problems.

Karas Celik and Ozcelik (2025) introduce the Assembly Line Rebalancing Problem with Human–Robot Collaboration. Keshvarparast et al. (2024) propose a novel mathematical model aimed at accelerating the ergonomic design of human–robot collaborative workstations.

Inkulu and Bahubalendruni (2023) study a human-robot collaborative task allocation. The proposed methodology is structured in two phases: (1) resource allocation and (2) resource estimation, both approached through an assembly line balancing perspective.

Zacharia et al. (2024) study the impact of integrating cobots into manual assembly lines with a focus on improving production rates and achieving workload smoothing across stations. They develop a GA and conduct simulation experiments to address the uncertainty inherent in manual task processing times by incorporating fuzziness into the simulation model.

Finally, recent research indicates a growing trend toward the hybridization of combinatorial optimization and artificial intelligence techniques.

8 Technology and IA

Kegyeges et al. (2024) develop a novel heuristic to target a dynamically pre-filtered action space for the reinforcement learning agent (dIOptRL algorithm) for disassembly line optimization with reinforcement learning.

Chu and Chen (2024) address the multi-manned DLBP with different work modes, focusing on the cost implications of variability in penalizing factors such as earliness and tardiness across products of varying scales. The authors propose a Reinforcement Learning-based Hyper-Heuristics approach. This method constructs a MDP to dynamically select from a set of low-level metaheuristic algorithms, while a multi-armed bandit framework is employed to fine-tune critical algorithmic parameters. Comparative computational experiments demonstrate the superiority of the proposed RLHs approach over conventional algorithms.

Yuan et al. (2024) develop a framework based on the principles of digital twin construction and object-oriented modelling. A piecewise coupling mechanism is introduced to capture the interaction between the physical and virtual components, alongside a multi-objective optimization algorithm tailored for the digital twin system. The optimization model incorporates three primary objectives: minimizing the overall task completion time, balancing workstation workloads by ensuring equitable task durations across stations and minimizing total production costs that include the cost of machine power consumption, resource cost, inventory cost and environmental cost.

Choi and Kim (2025) propose an integrated intelligent layout design framework that automatically generates an optimal layout based on specified requirements. The framework combines MIP, simulation-based optimization, and digital twin technology to iteratively perform assembly line balancing, cell and buffer optimization, and layout planning. This sequential and repeated process enables the automated derivation of layout designs that account for limited resources and physical constraints. The proposed approach has the potential to enhance productivity and operational efficiency in manufacturing environments.

Chu and Chen (2025) study HRC in two-sided partial DLBP with the aim to minimise energy consumption and maximise net revenue. The model addresses four interrelated sub-problems: planning disassembly sequences, selecting disassembly tasks, assigning tasks to mated-stations, and allocating human-robot resources. The authors develop a novel reinforcement-learning multi-objective evolutionary algorithm based on decomposition. This algorithm integrates an encoding/decoding scheme, reinforcement learning techniques, problem-specific characteristics, and coevolution between the sub-problems.

Contribution of the Special Issue:

Jabeur et al. (2024) propose an integrated lot sizing and flexible flow line scheduling model that operates under a time-of-use electricity pricing scheme. The model incorporates energy supply from conventional grid sources, on-site renewable generation, and an energy storage system. A two-level optimization framework is developed to balance energy cost

minimization with production throughput and customer demand satisfaction. To manage the problem's complexity, a reinforcement learning-based solution methodology is introduced.

Weerasekara et al. (2024) propose a novel approach utilizing Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) to manage task control in disassembly systems. The authors examine the impact of DRL-driven policies on inventory accumulation and unmet demand. Furthermore, the generalizability of the DRL approach is demonstrated across three MDP configurations, incorporating Poisson-based arrivals and demands, product obsolescence, and variable processing rates.

8 Concluding remarks

A review of the literature confirms that the key trends identified by Battaia and Dolgui (2022) remain highly relevant in the domain of line balancing, and the contributions in this Special Issue further advance these directions which include the integration of multiple problem domains, the incorporation of sustainability criteria, the increasing focus on human factors, and the methodological evolution toward hybrid approaches combining multiple solution techniques including such AI tools as reinforcement learning.

The future of line balancing research lies in developing more holistic, integrated approaches that can address the complex challenges of modern manufacturing environments. These approaches must balance multiple objectives, incorporate human factors, leverage advanced technologies, and support sustainability goals.

As guest editors, we believe that this special issue provides a valuable snapshot of the current state of the art and will inspire further research in this important and evolving field. We express our gratitude to all the authors who contributed their work, the reviewers who ensured the high quality of the papers, and the editorial team of *Computers & Industrial Engineering* for their support throughout this process.

References:

- 1 Abdous, M.-A., Delorme, X., Battini, D., & Berger-Douce, S. (2023). Multi-objective collaborative assembly line design problem with the optimisation of ergonomics and economics. *International Journal of Production Research*, 61(22), 7830–7845.
- 2 Abdous, M.-A., Delorme, X., Battini, D., & Sgarbossa, F. (2025). Scenario-based optimization and simulation framework for human-centered Assembly Line Balancing. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 282, 109513.
- 3 Aguilar, H., García-Villoria, A., & Pastor, R. (2024). Heuristic and metaheuristic procedures for the Parallel Assembly Lines Balancing Problem with multi-line workstations and buffer sizing. *Computers & Operations Research*, 166, 106596.
- 4 Albus, M., Hornek, T., Kraus, W., & Huber, M. F. (2025). Towards scalability for resource reconfiguration in robotic assembly line balancing problems using a modified genetic algorithm. *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing*, 36(2), 1175–1199.
- 5 Albus, M., & Huber, M. F. (2023). Resource reconfiguration and optimization in brownfield constrained Robotic Assembly Line Balancing Problems. *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*, 67, 132–142.
- 6 Al-Fandi, L., & Almasarwah, N. (2025). Optimising and modeling the mixed-model two-sided disassembly line balancing problem with human-robot cooperation restrictions. *International Journal of Production Research*, 1–24.

- 7 Alfaro-Pozo, R., & Bautista-Valhondo, J. (2024). Impact of limiting the ergonomic risk on the economic and productive efficiency of an assembly line. *International Journal of Production Research*, 62(1/2), 122–140.
- 8 Alhomaini, E., & Askin, R. G. (2024). Exact and approximation heuristic of mixed model assembly line balancing with parallel lines and task-dependent tooling consideration. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 193, 110265
- 9 Álvarez-Miranda, E., Pereira, J., Vargas, C., & Vilà, M. (2023). Variable-depth local search heuristic for assembly line balancing problems. *International Journal of Production Research*, 61(9), 3102–3120.
- 10 Ameer, M., & Dahane, M. (2023). Reconfigurability improvement in Industry 4.0: a hybrid genetic algorithm-based heuristic approach for a co-generation of setup and process plans in a reconfigurable environment. *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing*, 34(3), 1445–1467.
- 11 Andreu-Casas, E., García-Villoria, A., & Pastor, R. (2022). Multi-manned assembly line balancing problem with dependent task times: a heuristic based on solving a partition problem with constraints. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 302(1), 96–116.
- 12 Bao, Z., Chen, L., & Qiu, K. (2023). An aircraft final assembly line balancing problem considering resource constraints and parallel task scheduling. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 182, 109436.
- 13 Battaïa, O., & Dolgui, A. (2022). Hybridizations in line balancing problems: A comprehensive review on new trends and formulations. *International Journal of Production Economics*, vol. 250, August 2022, 108673.
- 14 Battaïa, O., & Dolgui, A. (2013). A taxonomy of line balancing problems and their solution approaches. *International Journal of Production Economics*, vol. 142(2), pp. 259–2771.
- 15 Battaïa, O., Dolgui, A., & Guschinsky, N. (2023). MIP-based heuristics for combinatorial design of reconfigurable rotary transfer machines for production of multiple parts. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 262, 108904.
- 16 Battaïa, O., Dolgui, A., & Guschinsky, N. (2024). An exact method for machining lines design with equipment selection and line balancing. *International Journal of Production Research*, 62(1/2), 71–91.
- 17 Battarra, M., Fraboni, F., Thomasson, O., Erdogan, G., Laporte, G., & Formentini, M. (2020). Algorithms for the Calzedonia workload allocation problem. *The Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 72(9), 2004–2017.
- 18 Beldar, P., Fathi, M., Nourmohammadi, A., Delorme, X., Battaïa, O., & Dolgui, A. (2025). Transfer line balancing problem: A comprehensive review, classification, and research avenues. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 201, 110913.
- 19 Borreguero Sanchidrián, T., Portoleau, T., Artigues, C., García Sánchez, A., Ortega Mier, M., & Lopez, P. (2024). Large neighborhood search for an aeronautical assembly line time-constrained scheduling problem with multiple modes and a resource leveling objective. *Annals of Operations Research*, 338(1), 13–40.
- 20 Borsato Pinhão, J. da M. O., Ignacio, A. A. V., & Coelho, O. (2022). An integer programming mathematical model with line balancing and scheduling for standard work optimization: A realistic application to aircraft engines assembly lines. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 173, 108652.
- 21 Boysen, N., Schulze, P., & Scholl, A. (2021). Assembly line balancing: What happened in the last fifteen years? *European Journal of Operational Research*, vol. 301(3), pp. 797–8141.
- 22 Cai, M., Wang, G., Luo, X., & Xu, X. (2025a). Task allocation of human-robot collaborative assembly line considering assembly complexity and workload balance. *International Journal of Production Research*, 1–27.
- 23 Cai, J., Xue, H., Zheng, C., & Shi, H. (2025b). Improved dual-population genetic algorithm to solve human-robot collaborative assembly line balancing problem. *International Journal of Production Research*, 1–23.
- 24 Calzavara, M., Faccio, M., Finco, S., Persona, A., & Zennaro, I. (2025). A selection procedure for the design of mixed-model assembly systems considering walking workers and fixed workers. *International Journal of Production Research*, 63(3), 1028–1045.
- 25 Caterino, M., Rinaldi, M., & Fera, M. (2023). Digital ergonomics: an evaluation framework for the ergonomic risk assessment of heterogeneous workers. *International Journal of Computer Integrated Manufacturing*, 36(2), 239–259.
- 26 Cerqueus, A., & Delorme, X. (2023). Evaluating the scalability of reconfigurable manufacturing systems at the design phase. *International Journal of Production Research*, 61(23), 8080–8093.
- 27 Choi, S. H., & Kim, B. S. (2025). Intelligent factory layout design framework through collaboration between optimization, simulation, and digital twin. *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing*, 36(3), 1547–1561.
- 28 Chu, M., & Chen, W. (2024). Multi-manned disassembly line balancing problems for retired power batteries based on hyper-heuristic reinforcement. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 194, 110400.
- 29 Chu, M., & Chen, W. (2025). Human-robot cooperation two-sided partial disassembly line balancing problem. *International Journal of Production Research*, 1–26.

- 30 Çil, Z. A., Öztop, H., Diri Kenger, Z., & Kizilay, D. (2023). Integrating distributed disassembly line balancing and vehicle routing problem in supply chain: Integer programming, constraint programming, and heuristic algorithms. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 265, 109014.
- 31 Cui, F., Jiang, Z., Zhou, X., Zheng, J., & Geng, N. (2025). A configuration optimization approach for reconfigurable manufacturing system based on column-generation combined with graph neural network. *International Journal of Production Research*, 63(3), 970–991.
- 32 Degirmencioglu Demiralay, Y., & Kara, Y. (2024). Profit-oriented balancing of two-sided disassembly lines with resource-dependent task times. *Robotic Intelligence & Automation (RIA)*, 44(6), 910–921.
- 33 Delorme, X., Cerqueus, A., Gianessi, P., & Lamy, D. (2023). RMS balancing and planning under uncertain demand and energy cost considerations. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 261, 108873.
- 34 Delorme, X., & Gianessi, P. (2024). Line balancing and task scheduling to minimise power peak of reconfigurable manufacturing systems. *International Journal of Production Research*, 62(14), 5061–5086.
- 35 Diefenbach, J., & Stollitz, R. (2022). Stochastic assembly line balancing: General bounds and reliability-based branch-and-bound algorithm. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 302(2), 589–605.
- 36 Didden, J. B. H. C., Lefeber, E., Adan, I. J. B. F., & Panhuijzen, I. W. F. (2023). Genetic algorithm and decision support for assembly line balancing in the automotive industry. *International Journal of Production Research*, 61(10), 3377–3395.
- 37 Diri Kenger, Z., Koç, Ç., & Özceylan, E. (2020). Integrated disassembly line balancing and routing problem. *International Journal of Production Research*, 58(23), 7250–7268.
- 38 Dolgui, A. (2006). Balancing Assembly and Transfer Lines. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 168(3), 663–6651.
- 39 Durmaz, N., & Budak, A. (2025). An integrated Bi-objective green vehicle routing and partial disassembly line problem for electronic waste: an industrial case study. *International Journal of Computer Integrated Manufacturing*, 38(3), 408–433.
- 40 Ehm, F. (2024). Scheduling and process planning for the dismantling shop with flexible disassembly mode and recovery level. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 189, 109927.
- 41 El Ahmadi, S. E. A., & El Abbadi, L. (2022). Reducing flow time in an automotive asynchronous assembly line: An application from an automotive factory. *Management & Production Engineering Review*, 13(1), 99–106.
- 42 El Houd, A., Piranda, B., De Matos, R., & Bourgeois, J. (2024). Swarm intelligence-based framework for accelerated and optimized assembly line design in the automotive industry. *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing*, 35(6), 2829–2843.
- 43 Elyasi, M., Selcuk, Y. S., Özener, O. Ö., & Coban, E. (2024). Imperialist competitive algorithm for unrelated parallel machine scheduling with sequence-and-machine-dependent setups and compatibility and workload constraints. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 190, 110086.
- 44 Faccio, M., Granata, I., Menini, A., Milanese, M., Rossato, C., Bottin, M., Minto, R., Pluchino, P., Gamberini, L., Boschetti, G., & Rosati, G. (2023). Human factors in cobot era: a review of modern production systems features. *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing*, 34(1), 85–106.
- 45 Faccio, M., Granata, I., & Minto, R. (2024). Task allocation model for human-robot collaboration with variable cobot speed. *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing*, 35(2), 793–806.
- 46 Fang, Y., Li, Z., Wang, S., & Lu, X. (2024). Multi-objective multi-fidelity optimisation for position-constrained human-robot collaborative disassembly planning. *International Journal of Production Research*, 62(11), 3872–3889.
- 47 Fathi, M., Sepehri, A., Ghobakhloo, M., Iranmanesh, M., & Tseng, M.-L. (2024). Balancing assembly lines with industrial and collaborative robots: Current trends and future research directions. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 193, 110254.
- 48 Feng, J., & Che, A. (2023). A note on integrated disassembly line balancing and routing problem. *International Journal of Production Research*, 61(9), 3144–3150.
- 49 Finnah, B., Gönsch, J., & Otto, A. (2025). Overcoming poor data quality: Optimizing validation of precedence relation data. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 322(3), 740–752.
- 50 Fink, C., Bodin, U., & Schelén, O. (2025). Why decision support systems are needed for addressing the theory-practice gap in assembly line balancing. *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*, 79, 515–527.
- 51 Gartner, M. A., Grenzfurtnner, W., Zauner, B., & Gronalt, M. (2024). Job and product rotation for maximising the production output on multi mixed-model assembly lines for element prefabrication in industrialised housebuilding. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 190, 110041.
- 52 Giridhar, M. P., & Panicker, V. V. (2024). Effect of ergonomic aspects on single- and multiproduct assembly-line balancing problems. *Human Factors & Ergonomics in Manufacturing & Service Industries*, 34(6), 491–515.

- 53 Goksoy Kalaycilar, E., Azizoğlu, M., & Batun, S. (2024). Disassembly line balancing with hazardous task failures – Model based solution approaches. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 190, 110089
- 54 Goksoy Kalaycilar, E., Batun, S., & Azizoğlu, M. (2022). A stochastic programming approach for the disassembly line balancing with hazardous task failures. *International Journal of Production Research*, 60(10), 3237–3262.
- 55 Grenzfurtner, W., Pichler, E., & Gronalt, M. (2024). Increasing the output of mixed-model assembly lines for industrialised housebuilding: learnings from a case-based simulation study. *International Journal of Production Research*, 1–16.
- 56 Güler, E., Kalayci, C. B., Ilgin, M. A., Özceylan, E., & Güngör, A. (2024). Advances in partial disassembly line balancing: A state-of-the-art review. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 188, 109898.
- 57 Güner, F., Görür, A. K., Satır, B., Kandiller, L., & Drake, J. H. (2024). A constraint programming approach to a real-world workforce scheduling problem for multi-manned assembly lines with sequence-dependent setup times. *International Journal of Production Research*, 62(9), 3212–3229.
- 58 Guo, X., Zhang, Z., Qi, L., Liu, S., Tang, Y., & Zhao, Z. (2022). Stochastic Hybrid Discrete Grey Wolf Optimizer for Multi-Objective Disassembly Sequencing and Line Balancing Planning in Disassembling Multiple Products. *IEEE Transactions on Automation Science & Engineering*, 19(3), 1744–1756.
- 59 Guo, H., Zhang, L., Ren, Y., Li, Y., Zhou, Z., & Wu, J. (2023). Optimizing a stochastic disassembly line balancing problem with task failure via a hybrid variable neighborhood descent-artificial bee colony algorithm. *International Journal of Production Research*, 61(7), 2307–2321.
- 60 Guo, L., Zhang, Z., Wu, T., Zhang, Y., Zeng, Y., & Xie, X. (2024). Green and efficient-oriented human-robot hybrid partial destructive disassembly line balancing problem from non-disassemblability of components and noise pollution. *Robotics & Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*, 90, 102816.
- 61 Habibi, M. K., Hammami, R., Battaia, O., & Dolgui, A. (2024). Simultaneous pickup-and-delivery production-routing problem in closed-loop supply chain with remanufacturing and disassembly consideration. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 273, 109290.
- 62 Hashemi-Petroodi, S. E., Thevenin, S., Kovalev, S., & Dolgui, A. (2022). Model-dependent task assignment in multi-manned mixed-model assembly lines with walking workers. *Omega*, 113, 102688.
- 63 Hashemi-Petroodi, S. E., Thevenin, S., Kovalev, S., & Dolgui, A. (2023). Markov decision process for multi-manned mixed-model assembly lines with walking workers. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 255, 108661.
- 64 He, J., Chu, F., Dolgui, A., & Anjos, M. F. (2024). Multi-objective disassembly line balancing and related supply chain management problems under uncertainty: Review and future trends. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 272, 109257.
- 65 He, Y., Smith, M. L., Thevenin, S., & Dolgui, A. (2024). Dynamic workload balancing to part input sequencing for integrated scheduling decision-making of flexible manufacturing systems. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 198, 110672.
- 66 He, J., Chu, F., Dolgui, A., Zheng, F., & Liu, M. (2022). Integrated stochastic disassembly line balancing and planning problem with machine specificity. *International Journal of Production Research*, 60(5), 1688–1708.
- 67 Hervouet, T., Panagou, S., & Sgarbossa, F. (2025). AS-IS representation and strategic framework for the design and implementation of a disassembly system. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 202, 110975.
- 68 Hu, P., Chu, F., Dolgui, A., Chu, C., & Liu, M. (2024). Integrated multi-product reverse supply chain design and disassembly line balancing under uncertainty. *Omega*, 126, 103062.
- 69 Huang, Y., Sheng, B., Luo, R., Lu, Y., Fu, G., & Yin, X. (2024). Solving human-robot collaborative mixed-model two-sided assembly line balancing using multi-objective discrete artificial bee colony algorithm. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 187, 109776.
- 70 Huang, Y., & Zhou, B. (2024). Trigonometric-based mechanisms hybridized African vulture optimization algorithm for multi-manned disassembly line balancing involving worker heterogeneity and collaboration. *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing*, 1–57.
- 71 Huchzermeier, A., & Mönch, T. (2023). Mixed-model assembly lines with variable takt and open stations. *Production & Operations Management*, 32(3), 704–722.
- 72 Inkulu, A. K., & Bahubalendruni, M. V. A. R. (2023). Optimal resource allocation for multiple shop floor tasks in collaborative assembly. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 185, 109695.
- 73 Işık, E. E., & Yildiz, S. T. (2024). Integer and constraint programming models for the straight and U-shaped assembly line balancing with hierarchical worker assignment problem. *International Journal of Production Research*, 62(14), 5269–5292.

- 74 Jabeur, M. H., Mahjoub, S., Toublanc, C., & Cariou, V. (2024). Optimizing integrated lot sizing and production scheduling in flexible flow line systems with energy scheme: A two level approach based on reinforcement learning. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 190, 110095.
- 75 Jung, W.-K., Kim, H., Park, Y.-C., Lee, J.-W., & Suh, E. S. (2022). Real-time data-driven discrete-event simulation for garment production lines. *Production Planning & Control*, 33(5), 480–491.
- 76 Kang, H.-Y., & Lee, A. H. I. (2023). An evolutionary genetic algorithm for a multi-objective two-sided assembly line balancing problem: a case study of automotive manufacturing operations. *Quality Technology & Quantitative Management*, 20(1), 66–88.
- 77 Karas Celik, A., & Ozcelik, F. (2025). Assembly line rebalancing problem with human-robot collaboration and a hyper-matheuristic solution approach. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 200, 110795.
- 78 Katirae, N., Calzavara, M., Finco, S., Battaia, O., & Battini, D. (2023). Assembly line balancing and worker assignment considering workers' expertise and perceived physical effort. *International Journal of Production Research*, 61(20), 6939–6959.
- 79 Kegyes, T., Süle, Z., & Abonyi, J. (2024). Disassembly line optimization with reinforcement learning. *Central European Journal of Operations Research*, 32(4), 1115–1142.
- 80 Keshvarparast, A., Berti, N., Chand, S., Guidolin, M., Lu, Y., Battaia, O., Xu, X., & Battini, D. (2024). Ergonomic design of Human-Robot collaborative workstation in the Era of Industry 5.0. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 198, 110729.
- 81 Keshvarparast, A., Katirae, N., Finco, S., & Calzavara, M. (2025). Integrating collaboration scenarios and workforce individualization in collaborative assembly line balancing. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 279, 109450.
- 82 Kheirabadi, M., Keivanpour, S., Chinniah, Y. A., & Frayret, J.-M. (2023). Human-robot collaboration in assembly line balancing problems: Review and research gaps. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 186, 109737.
- 83 Kheirabadi, M., Keivanpour, S., Frayret, J.-M., & Chinniah, Y. (2025). Safety-driven optimisation of human-robot collaborative assembly line balancing. *International Journal of Production Research*, 1–26.
- 84 Kim, H.-I., Youn, A.-J., & Lee, D.-H. (2025). A mathematical model and solution algorithms for optimising system-level configurations of reconfigurable single part flow lines. *International Journal of Production Research*, 63(1), 9–25.
- 85 Kose, Y., Ayyildiz, E., & Cevikcan, E. (2024). Evaluation of disassembly line layouts using an integrated fermatean fuzzy decision-making methodology: An application for refrigerator disassembly line. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 190, 110090.
- 86 Kose, Y., Cevikcan, E., Ertemel, S., & Murat, M. (2023). Game theory-oriented approach for disassembly line worker assignment and balancing problem with multi-manned workstations. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 181, 109294.
- 87 Kubilay, B., Öztop, H., & Çil, Z. A. (2024). Constraint programming models for parallel robotic assembly line balancing problems considering energy-efficiency. *Flexible Services & Manufacturing Journal*, 1–42.
- 88 Lahrichi, Y., Damand, D., Deroussi, L., Grangeon, N., & Norre, S. (2023). Investigating two variants of the sequence-dependent robotic assembly line balancing problem by means of a split-based approach. *International Journal of Production Research*, 61(7), 2322–2338.
- 89 Lahrichi, Y., Gamoura, S. C., Damand, D., & Barth, M. (2025). Bi-objective minimization of energy consumption and cycle time for the robotic assembly line balancing problem: pseudo-polynomial case and reduced search space metaheuristic. *International Transactions in Operational Research*, 1.
- 90 Leite, W. K. dos S., Araújo, A. J. da S., Silva, L. B. da, Costa, L. C. A. da, Silva, J. M. N. da, Vieira, E. M. de A., Souza, E. L. de, Kramer, H. H. F. R., & Oliveira, R. C. (2024). Job rotations based on physical and psychological workloads: A proposal for the footwear industry. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 188, 109887.
- 91 Li, Z., Kucukkoc, I., & Tang, Q. (2021). Enhanced branch-bound-remember and iterative beam search algorithms for type II assembly line balancing problem. *Computers & Operations Research*, 131, Article 105235.
- 92 Li, Y., Li, Z., & Saldanha-da-Gama, F. (2022). New approaches for rebalancing an assembly line with disruptions. *International Journal of Computer Integrated Manufacturing*, 35(10/11), 1059–1076.
- 93 Li, Y., Saldanha-da-Gama, F., Liu, M., & Yang, Z. (2023). A risk-averse two-stage stochastic programming model for a joint multi-item capacitated line balancing and lot-sizing problem. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 304(1), 353–365.
- 94 Li, Y., Qiao, Z., Chi, Y., Guo, L., & Yan, R. (2024a). Robotic assembly line balancing considering the carbon footprint objective with cross-station design. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 190, 110045
- 95 Li, Z., Sikora, C. G. S., & Kucukkoc, I. (2024b). Chance-constrained stochastic assembly line balancing with branch, bound and remember algorithm. *Annals of Operations Research*, 335(1), 491–516.

- 97 Li, M., & Zhou, B. (2025). Optimising work-sharing in disassembly line balancing problems: a multi-cycle strategy. *International Journal of Production Research*, 1–28.
- 98 Liang, J., Guo, S., Du, B., Liu, W., & Zhang, Y. (2022). Restart genetic flatworm algorithm for two-sided disassembly line balancing problem considering negative impact of destructive disassembly. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 355, 131708.
- 99 Liang, W., Zhang, Z., Yin, T., Zhang, Y., & Wu, T. (2023a). Modelling and optimisation of energy consumption and profit-oriented multi-parallel partial disassembly line balancing problem. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 262, 108928.
- 100 Liang, W., Zhang, Z., Zhang, Y., Xu, P., & Yin, T. (2023b). Improved social spider algorithm for partial disassembly line balancing problem considering the energy consumption involved in tool switching. *International Journal of Production Research*, 61(7), 2250–2266.
- 101 Liu, M., Liu, Z., Chu, F., Liu, R., Zheng, F., & Chu, C. (2022). Risk-averse assembly line worker assignment and balancing problem with limited temporary workers and moving workers. *International Journal of Production Research*, 60(23), 7074–7092.
- 102 Liu, Q., Wei, X., Wang, Q., Song, J., Lv, J., Liu, Y., & Tang, O. (2024). An investigation of mixed-model assembly line balancing problem with uncertain assembly time in remanufacturing. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 198, 110676.
- 103 Lopes, T. C., Michels, A. S., Brauner, N., & Magatão, L. (2023). Balancing-sequencing paced assembly lines: a multi-objective mixed-integer linear case study. *International Journal of Production Research*, 61(17), 5901–5917.
- 104 Louis, A., Alpan, G., Penz, B., & Benichou, A. (2023). Mixed-model sequencing versus car sequencing: comparison of feasible solution spaces. *International Journal of Production Research*, 61(10), 3415–3434.
- 105 Lovato, D., Guillaume, R., Thierry, C., & Battaïa, O. (2024). Aircraft final assembly line scheduling with user preferences and equity of work distribution. *Flexible Services & Manufacturing Journal*, 1–19.
- 106 Lu, J., Tsinarakis, G., Sarantinoudis, N., Arampatzis, G., Zheng, X., & Kiritsis, D. (2024). A semantic model-based systems engineering approach for assessing the operational performance of metal forming process. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 190, 110042.
- 107 Mao, Z., Sun, Y., Fang, K., Huang, D., & Zhang, J. (2024). Balancing and scheduling of assembly line with multi-type collaborative robots. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 271, 109207.
- 108 Mao, Z., Zhang, J., Sun, Y., Fang, K., & Huang, D. (2025). Balancing parallel assembly lines with human-robot collaboration: problem definition, mathematical model and tabu search approach. *International Journal of Production Research*, 63(1), 51–85.
- 109 Melega, G. M., Belgarch, S., Jans, R., & Paquette, J. (2024). A line balancing problem with parallel workers and cycle time minimization. *INFOR*, 1–31.
- 110 Mellouli, A., Mellouli, R., Triki, H., & Masmoudi, F. (2024). An efficient hybridization of ant colony optimization and genetic algorithm for an assembly line balancing problem of type 2 under zoning constraints. *Annals of Operations Research*, 1–33.
- 111 Meng, K., Tang, Q., & Zhang, Z. (2023). Balancing and sequencing of mixed-model assembly line considering preventive maintenance scenarios: mathematical model and a migrating birds optimization algorithm. *Flexible Services & Manufacturing Journal*, 35(4), 1175–1205.
- 112 Mete, S., Serin, F., Çil, Z. A., Çelik, E., & Özceylan, E. (2023). A comparative analysis of meta-heuristic methods on disassembly line balancing problem with stochastic time. *Annals of Operations Research*, 321(1/2), 371–408.
- 113 Mezghani, Y., Hashemi-Petroodi, S. E., Thevenin, S., & Dolgui, A. (2024). Robust design and reconfiguration planning of mixed-model assembly lines under uncertain evolutions of product family. *International Journal of Production Research*, 62(13), 4957–4979.
- 114 Michels, A. S., & Costa, A. M. (2022). Mixed-integer linear programming models for the type-II resource-constrained assembly line balancing problem. *Assembly Automation*, 42(5), 585–594.
- 115 Michels, A. S., & Costa, A. M. (2024). Model and heuristics for the multi-manned assembly line worker integration and balancing problem. *International Journal of Production Research*, 62(24), 8719–8744.
- 116 Moncayo, M. L. A., He, N., & Arias, N. E. H. (2025). Minimising by Simulation-Based Optimisation the Cycle Time for the Line Balancing Problem in Real-World Environments. *Applied Stochastic Models in Business & Industry*, 41(1), 1–18.
- 117 Mönch, T., Huchzermeier, A., & Bebersdorf, P. (2022). Variable takt time groups and workload equilibrium. *International Journal of Production Research*, 60(5), 1535–1552.

- 118 Monguzzi, A., Maria Zanchettin, A., & Rocco, P. (2024). A systematic strategy for the architecture design of collaborative and reconfigurable assembly lines. *International Journal of Production Research*, 62(24), 8880–8903.
- 119 Mumtaz, J., Minhas, K. A., Rauf, M., Yue, L., & Chen, Y. (2024). Solving line balancing and AGV scheduling problems for intelligent decisions using a Genetic-Artificial bee colony algorithm. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 189, 109976.
- 120 Nourmohammadi, A., Arbaoui, T., Fathi, M., & Dolgui, A. (2025). Balancing human–robot collaborative assembly lines: A constraint programming approach. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 2025, 111154.
- 121 Nourmohammadi, A., Fathi, M., & Ng, A. H. C. (2024). Balancing and scheduling human-robot collaborated assembly lines with layout and objective consideration. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 187, 109775.
- 122 Ostovari, A., Benyoucef, L., Haddou Benderbal, H., & Delorme, X. (2025). Enhancing scalable reconfigurable manufacturing systems through robust optimisation: energy efficiency and cost minimisation under uncertainty. *International Journal of Production Research*, 63(8), 3064–3089.
- 123 Peng, Y., Zhang, L., Xia, B., & Han, Y. (2023). Research on balancing and sequencing problems of flexible mixed model assembly lines with alternative precedence relations. *International Journal of Production Research*, 61(24), 8451–8467.
- 124 Pereira, J., & Ritt, M. (2022). A note on “Algorithms for the Calzedonia workload allocation problem.” *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 73(6), 1420–1422.
- 125 Pereira, J., & Ritt, M. (2023). Exact and heuristic methods for a workload allocation problem with chain precedence constraints. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 309(1), 387–398.
- 126 Petersen, J., Nourmohammadi, A., Fathi, M., Ghobakhloo, M., & Tavana, M. (2025). Line balancing for energy efficiency in production: A qualitative and quantitative literature analysis. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 205, 111144.
- 127 Petzoldt, C., Harms, M., & Freitag, M. (2023). Review of task allocation for human-robot collaboration in assembly. *International Journal of Computer Integrated Manufacturing*, 36(11), 1675–1715.
- 128 Pitakaso, R., Sethanan, K., Jirasirilerd, G., & Golinska-Dawson, P. (2023). A novel variable neighborhood strategy adaptive search for SALBP-2 problem with a limit on the number of machine’s types. *Annals of Operations Research*, 324(1/2), 1501–1525.
- 129 Ponnambalam, S. G., Chang, Q., Zhong, R. Y., Kucukkoc, I., & Janardhanan, M. N. (2023). Human-Robot collaboration in the next generation manufacturing and logistics system. *Flexible Services & Manufacturing Journal*, 35(4), 975–978.
- 130 Possan Junior, M. C., Michels, A. S., & Magatão, L. (2023). An exact method to incorporate ergonomic risks in Assembly Line Balancing Problems. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 183, 109414.
- 131 Quenehen, A., Klement, N., Abdeljaouad, A. M., Roucoules, L., & Gibaru, O. (2023). Economic and ergonomic performance enhancement in assembly process through multiple collaboration modes between human and robot. *International Journal of Production Research*, 61(5), 1517–1531.
- 132 Rezvanizadeh, M., Mohammad-Ghasemi, M., Soltanzadeh, A., & Sadeghi-Yarandi, M. (2023). Development of a novel ergonomic index assessment in the workplace based on physical, cognitive, and environmental components. *Work*, 75(3), 1071–1086.
- 133 Şahin, M., & Kellegöz, T. (2023). Benders’ decomposition based exact solution method for multi-manned assembly line balancing problem with walking workers. *Annals of Operations Research*, 321(1/2), 507–540.
- 134 Şahin, M., & Kellegöz, T. (2024). Novel mathematical modelling approaches and a new lower bounding scheme for multi-manned assembly line balancing problems with walking workers. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 190, 110043.
- 135 Şahin, M. C., & Tural, M. K. (2023). Robotic stochastic assembly line balancing. *Flexible Services & Manufacturing Journal*, 35(4), 1076–1115.
- 136 Salveson, M. E. (1955). The assembly-line balancing problem. *Transactions of the American Society of Mechanical Engineers*, 77(6), 939–947.
- 137 Salatiello, E., Vespoli, S., Guizzi, G., & Grassi, A. (2024). Long-sighted dispatching rules for manufacturing scheduling problem in Industry 4.0 hybrid approach. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 190, 110006.
- 138 Sawik, T. (2024). A new MIP approach for balancing and scheduling of mixed model assembly lines with alternative precedence relations. *International Journal of Production Research*, 62(1/2), 110–121.
- 139 Schäfer, L., Tse, S., May, M. C., & Lanza, G. (2025). Assisted production system planning by means of complex robotic assembly line balancing. *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*, 78, 109–123.

- 140 Schibelbain, D., Lopes, T. C., & Magatão, L. (2024). A method to balancing robotic mixed-model assembly lines: Practical constraints, computational challenges, and performance estimation. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 197, 110595
- 141 Schmid, N. A., Montreuil, B., & Limère, V. (2024). Modeling and solving integrated assembly line balancing, assembly line feeding, and facility sizing problems. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 277, 109354.
- 142 Schulze, P., Scholl, A., & Walter, R. (2024). R-SALSA: A branch, bound, and remember algorithm for the workload smoothing problem on simple assembly lines. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 312(1), 38–55.
- 143 Sewell, E. C., & Jacobson, S. H. (2012). A branch, bound, and remember algorithm for the simple assembly line balancing problem. *INFORMS Journal on Computing*, 24(3), 343–515.
- 144 Shang, Y., Li, S., Li, P., & Liu, J. (2024). An adaptable scheduling model for mixed flexible flow line with production continuity and processing capacity. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 192, 110239.
- 145 Shibasaki, R. S., Rossi, A., & Gurevsky, E. (2024). A new upper bound based on Dantzig-Wolfe decomposition to maximize the stability radius of a simple assembly line under uncertainty. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 313(3), 1015–1030.
- 146 Sikora, C. G. S. (2024). Balancing mixed-model assembly lines for random sequences. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 314(2), 597–611.
- 147 Sikora, C. G. S., & Tiacci, L. (2025). Incorporating car-sequencing rules in the planning of mixed-model assembly lines. *International Journal of Production Research*, 63(6), 2114–2132.
- 148 Sikora, C. G. S., & Weckenborg, C. (2023). Balancing of assembly lines with collaborative robots: comparing approaches of the Benders' decomposition algorithm. *International Journal of Production Research*, 61(15), 5117–5133.
- 149 Singh, R. K., Singh, A. R., Yadav, R. K., & Upadhyay, R. K. (2023). A station crashing-based recursive approach for disassembly line balancing problem in the presence of task failure. *International Journal of Production Research*, 61(16), 5659–5675.
- 150 Slama, R., Slama, I., Tlahig, H., Slangen, P., & Ben-Ammar, O. (2024). An overview on human-centred technologies, measurements and optimisation in assembly systems. *International Journal of Production Research*, 62(14), 5336–5358.
- 151 Sordan, J. E., Oprime, P. C., Pimenta, M. L., Lombardi, F., & Chiabert, P. (2022). Symbiotic relationship between robotics and Lean Manufacturing: a case study involving line balancing. *TQM Journal*, 34(5), 1076–1095.
- 152 Soysal-Kurt, H., İşleyen, S. K., & Gökçen, H. (2025). Balancing and sequencing of mixed-model parallel robotic assembly lines considering energy consumption. *Flexible Services & Manufacturing Journal*, 37(1), 38–66.
- 153 Stade, D., Spoor, J. M., Manns, M., & Ovtcharova, J. (2024). Process time distribution simulation in robotic assembly line balancing. *International Journal of Production Research*, 1–18.
- 154 Sun, X., Guo, S., Guo, J., Du, B., Yang, Z., & Wang, K. (2024). A Pareto-based hybrid genetic simulated annealing algorithm for multi-objective hybrid production line balancing problem considering disassembly and assembly. *International Journal of Production Research*, 62(13), 4809–4830.
- 155 Tasoglu, G., & Ilgin, M. A. (2024). A simulation-based genetic algorithm approach for the simultaneous consideration of reverse logistics network design and disassembly line balancing with sequencing. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 187, 109794.
- 156 Telemeci, Y. E., & Azizoğlu, M. (2024). Type-II transfer line balancing problem – A branch and bound approach. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 198, 110689.
- 157 Tiacci, L. (2024a). Assigning rest times to workers in assembly lines with ergonomically hazardous tasks: an approach to defend companies' profitability. *International Journal of Production Research*, 62(4), 1239–1261.
- 158 Tiacci, L. (2024b). Combining balancing, sequencing and buffer allocation decisions to improve the efficiency of mixed-model asynchronous assembly lines. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 194, 110357.
- 159 Tian, G., Liu, J., Zhang, X., Truong Pham, D., Guo, X., Du, Y., Zhao, C., & Li, H. (2024). Multi-objective disassembly line design and optimisation considering energy efficiency and human factors. *Journal of Engineering Design*, 1–29.
- 160 Torkul, O., Selvi, İ. H., Şişci, M., & Öge, M. (2024). An integrated simulation-data envelopment analysis approach for impact of line-seru conversion. *RAIRO: Operations Research (2804-7303)*, 58(6), 4819–4859.
- 161 Tremblet, D., Yelles-Chaouche, A. R., Gurevsky, E., Brahimi, N., & Dolgui, A. (2023). Optimizing task reassignments for reconfigurable multi-model assembly lines with unknown order of product arrival. *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*, 67, 190–200.

- 162 Troncoso, N., Cancela, H., Piñeyro, P., Quezada, F., & Vásquez, Ó. C. (2024). The product–mold–machine manufacturing problem: Complexity, MILP models and constructive heuristics. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 189, 109937.
- 163 Tropschuh, B., Cegarra, J., & Battaia, O. (2024). Integrating physiological and mental aspects in employee scheduling: an overview for practitioners in production management. *International Journal of Production Research*, 62(6), 2093–2106.
- 164 Tuo, Y., Zhang, Z., Wu, T., Zeng, Y., Zhang, Y., & Junqi, L. (2024). Multimanned disassembly line balancing optimization considering walking workers and task evaluation indicators. *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*, 72, 263–286.
- 165 Vahedi-Nouri, B., Tavakkoli-Moghaddam, R., Hanzálek, Z., & Dolgui, A. (2024). Production scheduling in a reconfigurable manufacturing system benefiting from human-robot collaboration. *International Journal of Production Research*, 62(3), 767–783.
- 166 Wang, K., Guo, J., Du, B., Li, Y., Tang, H., Li, X., & Gao, L. (2023). A novel MILP model and an improved genetic algorithm for disassembly line balancing and sequence planning with partial destructive mode. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 186, 109704.
- 167 Weerasekara, S., Li, W., Isaacs, J., & Kamarthi, S. (2024). Reinforcement learning for disassembly task control. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 190, 110044.
- 168 Wei, N.-C., Liu, S.-F., Chen, C.-H., Xu, Y.-X., & Shih, Y.-Y. (2023). An Integrated Method for Solving the Two-Sided Assembly Line Balancing Problems. *Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Systems*, 22(1), 181–203.
- 169 Wu, J., Shang, J., Wang, J., Li, Z., Wu, Z., & Xiao, L. (2024). A Decomposition Approach for Sequencing Mixed-Model Two-Sided Assembly Line with Stochastic Processing Time. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Operational Research*, 1.
- 170 Wu, T., Zhang, Z., Zeng, Y., & Zhang, Y. (2024a). Mixed-integer programming model and hybrid local search genetic algorithm for human–robot collaborative disassembly line balancing problem. *International Journal of Production Research*, 62(5), 1758–1782.
- 171 Wu, T., Zhang, Z., Zeng, Y., Zhang, Y., Guo, L., & Liu, J. (2024b). Techno-economic and environmental benefits-oriented human–robot collaborative disassembly line balancing optimization in remanufacturing. *Robotics & Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*, 86, 102650.
- 172 Yelles-Chaouche, A. R., Gurevsky, E., Brahimi, N., & Dolgui, A. (2022). Minimizing task reassignments under balancing multi-product reconfigurable manufacturing lines. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 173, 108660.
- 173 Yelles-Chaouche, A. R., Gurevsky, E., Brahimi, N., & Dolgui, A. (2024). Optimizing modular equipment in the design of multi-product reconfigurable production lines. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 192, 110226.
- 174 Yeni, F. B., Cevikcan, E., Yazici, B., & Yilmaz, O. F. (2024). Aggregated planning to solve multi-product multi-period disassembly line balancing problem by considering multi-manned stations: A generic optimization model and solution algorithms. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 196, 110464.
- 175 Yin, T., Wu, J., Cao, J., Huang, Y., Li, C., & Long, J. (2025). Multi-man–robot collaborative disassembly line balancing optimization via mixed-integer programming and genetic Jaya algorithm. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 490, 144695.
- 176 Yin, T., Zhang, Z., Wu, T., Zeng, Y., Zhang, Y., & Liu, J. (2023). Multimanned partial disassembly line balancing optimization considering end-of-life states of products and skill differences of workers. *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*, 66, 107–126.
- 177 Yetkin, B. N., & Kahya, E. (2022). A bi-objective ergonomic assembly line balancing model with conic scalarization method. *Human Factors & Ergonomics in Manufacturing & Service Industries*, 32(6), 494–507.
- 178 Yilmaz, B. G., Yilmaz, Ö. F., & Çevikcan, E. (2023). Lot streaming in workforce scheduling problem for seru production system under Shojinka philosophy. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 185, 109680.
- 179 Yuan, G., Liu, X., Zhu, C., Wang, C., Zhu, M., & Sun, Y. (2024). Multi-objective coupling optimization of electrical cable intelligent production line driven by digital twin. *Robotics & Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*, 86, 102682.
- 180 Zacharia, P. T., Xidias, E. K., & Nearchou, A. C. (2024). The fuzzy human-robot collaboration assembly line balancing problem. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 187, 109774.
- 181 Zangaro, F., Minner, S., & Battini, D. (2023). The multi-manned joint assembly line balancing and feeding problem. *International Journal of Production Research*, 61(16), 5543–5565.
- 182 Zeng, Y., Zhang, Z., Liang, W., & Zhang, Y. (2023). Balancing optimization for disassembly line of mixed homogeneous products with hybrid disassembly mode. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 185, 109646.

- 183 Zeng, Y., Zhang, Z., Yin, T., & Zheng, H. (2022). Robotic disassembly line balancing and sequencing problem considering energy-saving and high-profit for waste household appliances. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 381, 135209.
- 184 Zeng, Y., Zhang, Z., Zhang, Y., Liang, W., & Song, H. (2025). Modelling and optimization of line efficiency for preventive maintenance of robot disassembly line. *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*, 79, 347–363.
- 185 Zhang, Z., Guo, L., Zhang, Y., Zeng, Y., Song, H., Li, Y., Chen, H., & Aslam, M. W. (2025). Industrial application of multi-robot destructive disassembly line balancing under component non-disassemblability for multi-product scenarios. *International Journal of Production Research*, 1–26.
- 186 Zhang, M., Li, L., Liu, S., Li, H., Mu, X., & Yin, F. (2024a). Selection of disassembly schemes for multiple types of waste mobile phones based on knowledge reuse and disassembly line balancing. *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*, 76, 207–221.
- 187 Zhang, X., Tian, G., Fathollahi-Fard, A. M., Pham, D. T., Li, Z., Pu, Y., & Zhang, T. (2024b). A chance-constraint programming approach for a disassembly line balancing problem under uncertainty. *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*, 74, 346–366.
- 188 Zhang, Y., Zhang, Z., Guan, C., & Xu, P. (2022). Improved whale optimisation algorithm for two-sided disassembly line balancing problems considering part characteristic indexes. *International Journal of Production Research*, 60(8), 2553–2571.
- 189 Zhang, Z., Zhu, L., Chen, Y., & Guan, C. (2023). A multi-objective hybrid evolutionary search algorithm for parallel production line balancing problem including disassembly and assembly tasks. *International Transactions in Operational Research*, 30(6), 3508–3553.
- 190 Zheng, C., Li, Z., Janardhanan, M., Zhang, Z., & Zhang, L. (2025a). Balancing and scheduling human-robot collaborative assembly lines with heterogeneous robots and limited resources: Constraint programming approach and fruit fly optimization algorithm. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 203, 111046.
- 191 Zheng, C., Li, Z., Janardhanan, M., Zhang, Z., & Zhang, L. (2025b). Improved swarm-based metaheuristics for optimizing human–robot collaborative assembly lines with multi-type collaborative robots. *Flexible Services & Manufacturing Journal*, 1–63.
- 192 Zheng, C., Li, Z., Zhang, Z., Zhang, L., & Tang, Q. (2025c). Multi-objective restarted simulated annealing algorithm for assembly line balancing problem with collaborative robots considering ergonomics risks. *Flexible Services & Manufacturing Journal*, 1–39.
- 193 Zhou, Y., Guo, X., & Li, D. (2022). A dynamic programming approach to a multi-objective disassembly line balancing problem. *Annals of Operations Research*, 311(2), 921–944.
- 194 Zhu, L., Chen, Y., & Mumtaz, J. (2024). Multi-objective human-robot collaborative disassembly line balancing considering components remanufacture demand and hazard characteristics. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 197, 110621